

1 **Postcranial skeleton of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis* Goodwin,**
2 **1939) (Rodentia: Calomyscidae): shape, size, function and locomotor adaptation**

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32
33 **Abstract**

34 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis* Goodwin, 1939) is a poorly known
35 small rodent that occupies rocky habitats in Iran, Turkmenistan, Afghanistan, Pakistan,
36 Azerbaijan, and Syria. Herein, a detailed description of the shape, size, and function of the
37 postcranial skeleton of this species is presented for the first time. Trapping was carried out in
38 eastern Iran between the years 2013 and 2015. Skeletal parts of 24 adult male specimens were
39 removed using the papain digestion protocol, and several postcranial morphological characters
40 and measurements were examined. We attempted to achieve a morpho-functional
41 characterization of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse and to match morphological specializations
42 with previous information on the ecology, behavior and phylogenetic inferences of this rodent.
43 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse has extended transverse processes and long zygapophyses in the
44 first five caudal vertebrae along with a good innervation of the caudal vertebrae, which has
45 resulted in a well-developed basal musculature of the tail. It has extended forelimb, long ilium
46 and short post-acetabular part of the innominate bone, loose hip joint with high degree of lateral
47 movement of the hindlimb, and long distal elements of the hindlimb. These features have
48 resulted in fast terrestrial movements in open microhabitats, including climbing and jumping.
49 Although superficial scratching of the ground is observed, the species is incapable of digging
50 burrows. Evaluation of postcranial morphological characters and character states further

51 indicated the basal radiation of the genus *Calomyscus* among other Muroidea. Findings
52 constitute a source of information for morpho-functional and phylogenetic comparisons
53 between Calomyscidae and other mouse-like muroids.

54 55 **KEYWORDS**

56 Eco-morphological traits, Locomotory habits, Morpho-functional characterization,
57 Osteological characters, Skeletal system

58 59 **1. INTRODUCTION**

60 **1.1. Postcranial skeleton variations and adaptation**

61 Postcranium is referred to the whole or part of the skeleton, except the skull (cranium and
62 mandible), and consists of three structural and functional subunits: 1) vertebral column and
63 thorax (ribs and sternum), 2) pectoral girdle (clavicle and scapula) and forelimb, and 3) pelvic
64 girdle (innominate bone) and hindlimb (Martin, 2005). Numerous studies have revealed the
65 great morphological variations in the postcranial anatomy among various groups of mammals
66 (e.g., Polk et al., 2000; Argot, 2001; Narita & Kuratani, 2005; Schilling & Hackert, 2006; Polly,
67 2007; Williams et al., 2007; Lessa et al., 2008; Salton & Sargis, 2008; Alvarez et al., 2013;
68 Socha et al., 2015; Randau et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2018). In short, these differences in
69 postcranial morphology reflect differences in ecology and locomotor abilities, the interplay
70 between postcranial features and ecological niche, behavioral and ecological adaptations to
71 differing functional demands and phylogenetic constraints.

72 Several studies have examined postcranial characteristics of small mammals, including rodents
73 (e.g., Weisbecker & Schmid, 2007; Candela & Picasso, 2008; Morgan, 2008; Samuels & Van
74 Valkenburgh, 2008; Wilson & Sanchez-Villagra, 2010; Wilson et al., 2010; Morgan & Verzi,
75 2011; Alvarez et al., 2013; Araújo et al., 2013; Coutinho et al., 2013; Morgan & Álvarez, 2013;
76 Samuels et al., 2013; Carrizo et al., 2014; Ginot et al., 2016; Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017;
77 Koyabu, 2017; Pérez et al., 2017, 2021; Scheidt et al., 2019; Wölfer et al., 2019; Hamidi et al.,
78 2020a; Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020; Pérez & Diaz, 2020; Löffler et al., 2022). The studies on
79 the postcranial skeleton in rodents can be classified into two main groups: 1) investigations into
80 the locomotor system, which are generally related to the study of the long bones (mainly limbs
81 and especially in Muroidea), and focused on the relationship between postcranial skeletal
82 morphology and ecology, locomotor style and strategies, or life habits of the animal (e.g.,
83 Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Alvarez et al., 2013; Carrizo et al., 2014; Ginot et al.,
84 2016; Scheidt et al., 2019; Wölfer et al., 2019), 2) studies which show the variations of
85 postcranium in a phylogenetic context (e.g., Weisbecker & Schmid, 2007; Morgan, 2008;
86 Morgan & Álvarez, 2013; Coutinho & de Oliveira 2017; Hamidi et al., 2020a; Pérez et al.,
87 2021). However, the interplay between postcranial diversity and phylogenetic relationship
88 remains poorly understood, mainly due to the difficulties in preservation and cleaning of
89 postcranium and identifying postcranial characters, determining the effects of adaptation on
90 skeleton morphology, intraspecific polymorphism, or even basically less interests among the
91 researchers towards such classical studies. There are also a few studies which have determined
92 the morphological changes in skeletal components during growth and development (e.g.,
93 Wilson & Sanchez-Villagra, 2010; Wilson et al., 2010; Koyabu, 2017).

94 According to the traditional definition, qualitative and quantitative morphological traits (such
95 as the position of muscle attachments or the limb proportions) (e.g., Smith & Savage, 1956,
96 Carrano, 1999) or based on biomechanical definitions (e.g., Stein & Casinos, 1997), several
97 locomotor categories have been constructed for mammals as follows:

98 Aerial species are dominantly found on trees and rarely leave it, and have the ability to glide
99 over distances. They evolved a patagium, which serves them to extend leaps and soften landing
100 impact (Paskins et al., 2007). Arboreal lifestyle category including species who live in trees

101 and on the ground. They climb trees regularly, for shelter, nest building and foraging, or when
102 escaping predators. They can also occur in bushes and on rocks (Carrizo et al., 2014). This
103 group includes scansorial species, which are adapted to or specialized for climbing in trees,
104 rock piles or mountains. They spend at least some of their time climbing, while using the
105 ground and lower strata of the forest, the shrub layer and canopy as well (Vieira & Monteiro-
106 Filho, 2003). Terrestrial species usually move on the ground and do not show specializations
107 that restrict any particular activity (Carrizo et al., 2014). They may dig to make a burrow (but
108 not extensively) or show saltatorial behavior, rarely swim or climb, but never glide (Samuels
109 & Van Valkenburgh, 2008). Cursorial is used to describe species that frequently travel fast or
110 far on the ground. These animals are generally associated with open environments (Djawdan
111 & Garland, 1988). Members of the saltatorial lifestyle capable of jumping behavior are
112 characterized by simultaneous use of the hindlimbs, commonly bipedal. This group includes
113 species that progress with a series of leaps: they extend simultaneously both fore and hindlimbs,
114 lifting the body completely off the ground and move forward (Carrizo et al., 2014). Species
115 with the fossorial lifestyle regularly dig to build extensive burrows as shelter or for rearing
116 their young and foraging underground. They display a predominantly subterranean existence
117 (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Scheidt et al., 2019). Semi-fossorial species also dig to
118 build burrows for shelter, mostly using their forelimbs, but do not forage underground (Samuels
119 & Van Valkenburgh, 2008). Semi-aquatic species regularly swim for foraging, escape from the
120 predators or dispersal (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008).

121 In several groups of mammals, locomotion in different ecological niches and adaptation to
122 different functional demands (e.g., long-distance or high-speed movement), as well as different
123 substrate textures (e.g., branches, soft soils, rocky areas) have impacts on bones and
124 musculature properties. These involve the resistance of long bone deformation to specific forces
125 (Scheidt et al., 2019). The long bones are subject to loads imposed by both the action of flexor
126 and extensor muscles and the substrate resistance; as much as they are shorter and thicker, they
127 can provide more strength to resist force without breakage and/or deformation, as observed in
128 subterranean mammals. In other words, fossoriality is strongly related to the greater robustness
129 in long limb bones of the fore and hindlimbs (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Seckel &
130 Janis, 2008). In contrast, saltatorial rodents have elongated metatarsals. Furthermore,
131 elongation of femur and metatarsals are considered significant indicators of cursoriality in many
132 mammals (Weisbecker & Schmid, 2007; Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Seckel & Janis,
133 2008). Different bending loads are expected for climbing activities and high landing forces on
134 the limb bones are expected when leaping or gliding in arboreal and gliding species as compared
135 to fossorial species. However, terrestrial species show a more unidirectional loading pattern on
136 the limb bones (Burr et al., 1989; Polk et al., 2000).

137 Home range and speed are also related to the ecological requirements of the species and can
138 have effect on the morphology of bones: many small mammals living in habitats, in which
139 resources are little spread in space, have smaller home ranges. On the other hand, predation
140 avoiding strategies of prey or hunting strategy of predators can be associated with the speed
141 (Janis & Wilhelm, 1993; Johnson et al., 2000; Christiansen, 2002). Álvarez et al. (2013)
142 showed that variation in the size of the home range of some small to medium-sized mammals
143 is mostly related to some changes in the shape of tibia, while speed is associated with shape
144 variations in a set of postcranial elements, including lumbar vertebrae, pelvic bone and tibia.
145 Moreover, body mass is, in some cases, a significant factor to explain shape variations, since
146 it can have influence on the morphology of long limb bones. It has been demonstrated that with
147 increasing body mass in many tetrapod taxa, the overall bone robustness will increase (e.g.,
148 Doube et al., 2009; Ryan & Shaw, 2013; Mielke et al., 2018). Generally, while animals with
149 smaller body size tend to maintain a crouched posture, terrestrial mammals with larger body
150 mass tend to have an upright posture. They also have a more rigid and straight vertebral column,

151 which can support their body mass more efficiently and limits their locomotor repertoire.
152 Having more robust and sturdier limb bones reflected in overall positive allometry of bone
153 robustness variables (e.g., Alexander et al., 1979; Bou et al., 1987; Hildebrand, 1988b;
154 Christiansen, 2002; Garcia & Dasilva, 2006; Hayssen, 2008; Doube et al., 2018). Allometric
155 effects occur above 100 kg. Thus, in small mammals with smaller body size (mostly < 5 kg),
156 the skeleton is not subject to strong allometric effects, and thus, diversity in their locomotory
157 system is low (Biewener, 1990; Christiansen, 1999). Both allometric effects and phylogenetic
158 interferences can make it difficult to conclude a simple morpho-functional relationship for a
159 taxon. For example, larger taxa of small to medium-sized mammals showed an elongated
160 ischium and pubic symphysis compared to the ilium and acetabulum (Álvarez et al., 2013).
161 Moreover, the study of Wölfer et al. (2019) showed that the anteroposterior diameter of the
162 femoral midshaft is strongly correlated to body mass, but bears almost no lifestyle signal in
163 Sciuromorpha. In contrast, Álvarez et al. (2013) stated that lumbar vertebrae and tibia show
164 non-significant relationships with body mass in small to medium-sized mammals. Moreover,
165 when body mass increases, the musculoskeletal system has to increase in greater proportion to
166 sustain the same strength and support the body (Hildebrand, 1988a).
167 Studying the morphological correlations with locomotion in small mammals indicated that
168 those taxa that show more specialized types of locomotion (such as gliding and fossoriality) are
169 easily distinguished based on their postcranium morphology, but there is less obvious
170 separation among more generalist locomotor types (i.e., arboreal, terrestrial, and scansorial)
171 (Chen & Wilson, 2015; Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020). It is proposed that the more reliable
172 indicators across a broad taxonomic diversity are the more proximal elements, because they
173 reflect both the maneuverability of the limb across a range of postures and the weight-bearing
174 capacity of the limb. In contrast, the morphology of the more distal elements (especially the
175 tarsal bones) may reflect more precise aspects of limb positioning, and so may be more
176 subjected to phylogenetic differences (Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020).
177 Although for different small mammals, the ground topographic differences require several
178 capabilities in movement, it has been shown that kinematic movement and positioning of the
179 limbs of small mammals are fairly similar, regardless of the substrate differences (Fischer et
180 al., 2002). So as Jenkins (1974) proposed, there is a little difference between adaptations e.g.,
181 for terrestrial *vs.* arboreal locomotion in small mammals; at small body sizes, the perceived
182 environment, would be similar whether on the ground or in the trees. In contrast, as a hypothesis
183 stated by Mayr (1963), a shift into a new niche or adaptive zone is initiated by a change in
184 behavior. In this regard, several studies have recorded the anatomical differences between small
185 mammals of different habitat preferences (Argot, 2001; Szalay & Sargis, 2001; Sargis, 2002;
186 Chen & Wilson, 2015; Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020). Hence, despite similar locomotion, it has
187 been demonstrated that small mammals inhabiting different habitats (i.e., ground-dwelling *vs.*
188 arboreal tree-dwelling) can be distinguished by differentiations in postcranial morphology and
189 whole skeletal morphometrical analyses (e.g., Chen & Wilson, 2015; Kilbourne, 2017).

190

191 **1.2. Studied species**

192 Herein, we will study brush-tailed mice (Rodentia: Calomyscidae), which are a group of small-
193 sized rodents distributed along the Near East and Middle Asia (Kilpatrick, 2017). Although
194 they have a mouse-like appearance, brush-tailed mice had an early divergence from the rest of
195 the mouse-like rodents (Steppan et al., 2004). With their long and narrow hindfeet, they are
196 very agile and are able to climb and jump among tumbled boulders using their long tail for
197 balance (Kilpatrick, 2017; Hamidi et al., 2020b).

198 The Family Calomyscidae is the sole member of a clade that radiated earlier than the Muridae
199 (Steppan et al., 2004). Due to their early divergence, these rodents represent an interesting group
200 for morphological and evolutionary comparisons. Despite several studies on ecological,

201 behavioral, biological, morphological, genetics, karyological, and parasitological aspects of
202 these rodents (e.g., Meyer & Malikov, 1995, 1996; Graphodatsky et al., 2000; Meyer &
203 Malikov, 2000; Malikov et al., 2001; Morshed & Patton, 2002; Malikov et al., 2006; Norris et
204 al., 2008; Hamidi, 2015; Hamidi et al., 2015, 2017a,b, 2018, 2019, 2020b; Nassirkhani &
205 Hamidi, 2015), there are no data on the postcranial skeleton for this group. The only reference
206 related to this topic is Malikov et al. (2006) in which there are descriptive notes on baculum
207 and its calcification topology in *Calomyscus* showing some similarities with the golden hamster
208 (*Mesocricetus auratus* Waterhouse, 1839, family Cricetidae) in the localization of the
209 calcification centers of baculum.

210 There are nine known extant species within the family Calomyscidae, which all belong to a
211 single genus, *Calomyscus* (Kilpatrick, 2017; Dezhman et al., 2021). In general, species of
212 *Calomyscus* share generalized muroid (mouse-like) morphology, exhibit high phenotypic and
213 behavioral similarities, and share similar ecological features as well (Hamidi et al., 2017a;
214 Kilpatrick, 2017). Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis* Goodwin, 1939) has
215 been reported from rocky outcrops and semi-mountainous areas (with scattered vegetation) of
216 north, northeast, and central Iran, and small patches in south and southwest Turkmenistan as
217 well as northwest and western parts of Afghanistan (Kilpatrick, 2017). This species lives in
218 small colonies (which is probably constrained by available habitat), similarly to congeners, and
219 occupies well-drained, barren, rocky habitats in the foothills and mountains at elevations of 67-
220 3500 m (Malikov et al., 1999, Hamidi et al., 2017a, 2018). Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is a
221 small-sized rodent, with a body mass ranging from 18-21 g (Kilpatrick, 2017; Hamidi et al.,
222 2020b). It is both granivorous and herbivorous, similar to what is expected for mouse-like
223 rodents. This terrestrial ambulatory species is able to jump high (approximately 50 cm in
224 height), climbs and has fast terrestrial movements as well (Hamidi et al., 2017a, 2018;
225 Kilpatrick, 2017). It uses concealed rock crevices for nest sites and shelter, which is
226 accommodated using nesting materials such as fine grasses and plant substances, or sheep wool
227 (Kilpatrick, 2017). It has been observed that it can superficially scratch the ground to prepare a
228 substrate for resting or breeding newborn pups in captivity (Hamidi et al., 2018). However, the
229 absence of brush-tailed mice from valley floors has led to a hypothesis that they are incapable
230 of digging burrows (Kilpatrick, 2017).

231 Herein, we describe in detail the postcranial morphology of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, with
232 notes on the size, structure, and function. Two hypotheses were assumed concerning the
233 postcranial morphology and patterns of locomotion: 1) species living in open microhabitats
234 without dense undercover (including terrestrial, cursorial and saltatorial lifestyles) should
235 possess morphological traits associated with fast running and jumping, whereas species which
236 construct or modify subterranean nests (such as fossorial and semi-fossorial lifestyles) should
237 possess morphological traits associated with digging (whether using limbs, teeth, and/or head-
238 lift digging) (Schich, 1971; Stein, 2000; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009), and 2) a long tail and long
239 limbs (especially long hindfeet) are attributed to a high proportion of activity on the ground,
240 whereas a short tail and short hindfeet are related to more activity in burrows (Niethammer &
241 Krapp, 1978; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009). Integration of anatomical surveys with previous studies
242 may bring about novel findings; we are expecting to provide an important database for future
243 analyses in different fields of study, such as geometric morphometrics and morpho-functional
244 researches, and to generate new data that will allow phylogenetic inferences based on
245 morphological comparison between Calomyscidae, as the basal radiation of the mouse-like
246 muroids, and other Muroidea.

247

248 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

249 **2.1. Study area and sampling**

250 This study was carried out in two mountainous regions in eastern Iran, including: 1) Kopet-Dag
251 Mountains, near the Iran-Turkmenistan frontier, with 2251 m height in average, and 2) Khaje-
252 Morad heights, located in northeastern Iran, with an average elevation of approximately 1146
253 m. Trapping was performed between the years 2013 and 2015. Captured Goodwin's brush-tailed
254 mice were transferred to the animal house and kept in captivity for several months to be used
255 for further investigations (including biological, developmental, and behavioral studies in
256 captivity).

257 To minimize the potential influence of sex and age biases on anatomical evaluations, only adult
258 males (n= 24), which had been captured from various localities in the field (n= 19) or were first
259 generation born in captivity (n= 5), were included. Several signs were considered for age
260 determination in order to initially classify specimens into three age groups (juvenile, sub-adult
261 and adult), including appearance of the genitalia, weight, dorsal body pelage color, development
262 of the tail tuft, and molar cusp pattern (author's observation). The total body weight was taken
263 with a digital balance with an accuracy of 0.1 g. Euthanasia of rodents was performed using
264 100% CO₂ at a flow rate of 30-70% of chamber volume per minute (gradual displacement
265 method) in a place separated from the animal housing room, while the animal was kept as calm
266 as possible. Gas exposure continued until a sufficient period (at least one minute) after breathing
267 stopped to ensure the death, followed by opening the thoracic cavity as an unequivocal
268 secondary means of ensuring death. Trapping permission was already obtained for a doctoral
269 research project entitled "Revision of taxonomic characters of Calomyscidae (Rodentia) based
270 on Evo-Devo studies and species identification of its molecular clades in Iran based on
271 biosystematics studies" (No. 3/29121) from Ferdowsi University of Mashhad (FUM). Animal
272 care and experimental procedures were performed in compliance with the "Guidelines for the
273 care, keep and use of laboratory and experimental animals, FUM" (Darvish, 2015).
274 Identification of rodents was confirmed by molecular methods (for more details see Hamidi et
275 al., 2015, 2017a, 2020b). External measurements used in this study, including head and body
276 length, tail length, total body length, hindfoot length, ear length and the length of whiskers,
277 were taken with a Vernier caliper with an accuracy of 0.1 mm (Table 1).

278 [Table 1]

279

280 **2.2. Postcranial examination**

281 Skeletal parts of Goodwin's brush-tailed mice were removed using the papain digestion
282 protocol. Samples were fully soaked in 7% papain solution with pH= 7 and treated at 60 °C for
283 36~48 h following Luther (1949) protocol with some modifications. Whenever possible, bones
284 of the right side of the appendicular skeleton were examined. In some cases, when they were
285 damaged or missing, bones from the left side were used. All ribs (except the first one), xiphoid
286 process of sternum, all carpal and some tarsal bones (except calcaneus and talus), and terminal
287 phalange of digits of manus were not included in the study because they were not completely
288 removed or conserved in examined specimens.

289 The study involved two different approaches to analyze the postcranium: 1) description of
290 discrete characters (qualitative morphological traits), and 2) postcranial measurements
291 (morphometrics traits). Several postcranial morphological characters corresponding to the axial
292 and appendicular skeleton were observed under a stereo-microscope and a hand lens. The
293 examined osteological characters were selected because of their importance in functional
294 aspects, such as posture, locomotion mode, and specific attributes of animal movements
295 following three sources: 1) descriptive studies (e.g., Argot, 2001, 2002; Szalay & Sargis, 2001;
296 Sargis, 2002; Argot, 2003; Martin, 2005; Candela & Picasso, 2008; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009;
297 Salton & Sargis, 2008, 2009; Flores, 2009; Flores & Díaz, 2009; Carrizo et al., 2014; Coutinho
298 & de Oliveira, 2017; Pérez et al., 2017; Hamidi et al., 2020a), 2) published illustrations and

299 skeletal descriptions of mammals (e.g., Davis, 1964; Popesko et al., 1992; Evans, 1993; Bab et
300 al., 2007), and 3) personal observations of specimens of other rodents (e.g., Hamidi, 2011).
301 Images of osteological components were obtained with an optical stereo-microscope connected
302 to a digital camera. Morphological appearances of the vertebral column and thorax, pectoral
303 and pelvic girdles, fore and hindlimbs were drawn using a drawing tube connecting to a stereo-
304 microscope, and originally described for the species considering form, size, and anatomical
305 function. The nomenclature for the anatomical description (anatomical terminology) follows
306 that of previous studies on different groups of mammals, including rodents (e.g., Argot, 2001,
307 2002; Szalay & Sargis, 2001; Candela & Picasso, 2008; Salton & Sargis, 2008; Flores, 2009).
308 In Figures 1 to 13, morphological postcranial characters for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse are
309 shown.

310 Moreover, a total of 86 morphological characters were also examined (Table 2) following the
311 list of postcranial character states and postcranial character treatment (polarity) mentioned in
312 literature (e.g., Carleton, 1980; Steppan, 1995; Vassallo, 1998; Argot, 2003; Rose & Chinnery,
313 2004; Martin, 2005; Sánchez-Villagra et al., 2006; Bab et al., 2007; Weisbecker & Schmid,
314 2007; Lessa et al., 2008; Seckel & Janis, 2008; Flores, 2009; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009; Morgan,
315 2008; Carrizo et al., 2014; Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017; Hamidi et al., 2020a), in order to
316 provide a primary information source for evolution of characters and its relation to the early
317 divergence of *Calomyscus* and basal location in the phylogenetic trees in comparison with other
318 muroid rodents. These data will be useful for further phylogenetic studies. Character treatment
319 (polarity) for some of the examined qualitative morphological characters of postcranium in this
320 study are provided in Table 2. For each character, ancestral/derived or
321 ancestral/intermediate/derived character states have been considered, and the character states
322 observed in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse are shown by * in Table 2.

323 [Table 2]

324
325 Fifty five postcranial measurements were taken with a digital caliper to the nearest 0.01 mm
326 following the previous literature (e.g., Fernández et al., 2000; Essner & Scheibe, 2002;
327 Elissamburu & Vizcaíno, 2004; Doube et al., 2009; Hopkins & Davis, 2009; Kuncová & Frynta,
328 2009; Alvarez et al., 2013; Pérez et al., 2017). Moreover, bones of the Persian jird (*Meriones*
329 *persicus* (Blanford, 1875)), and the brown rat (*Rattus norvegicus* (Berkenhout, 1769)) as two
330 representatives of terrestrial rodents, the great gerbil (*Rhombomys opimus* Lichtenstein, 1823)
331 as a semi-fossorial rodent, and the small five-toed jerboa (*Scarturus elater* (Lichtenstein, 1825))
332 as a saltatorial rodent, were examined for morpho-functional comparisons. Measurements of
333 the steppe field mouse (*Apodemus witherbyi* (Thomas, 1902)) were also extracted from
334 Kuncová & Frynta (2009) as a rodent which shows similarities in the body shape and size; both
335 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse and steppe field mouse are murid small rodents showing mouse-
336 like appearance. See Figure 14 and Table 1 for a detailed description of the measurements.

337 For analysis of locomotor characteristics, measurements for 22 species (3 species for each of
338 the aerial, arboreal, saltatorial, fossorial, semi-fossorial, and semi-aquatic groups, and 4 species
339 for terrestrial group including Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse) were used as listed in Table 3.
340 Brown rat, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, great gerbil, Persian jird, small five-toed jerboa, and
341 steppe field mouse are related to the present study, while data for the rest of species are
342 extracted from Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008). Fifteen morphological indices were
343 calculated as follows:

344 Shoulder moment index (SMI): relates to the mechanical advantage of the function of pectoral
345 and deltoid muscles across the shoulder joint. Brachial index (BI): shows relative proportion
346 of proximal (humerus) and distal (radius) elements of the forelimb. Humeral robustness index
347 (HRI): indicates the ability of humerus to resist against bending and shearing stresses, showing
348 robustness of the bone. Humeral epicondylar index (HEB): shows relative area available for

349 the origins of the forearm muscles (flexors, pronators, and supinators). Olecranon length index
350 (OLI): indicates relative mechanical advantage of the dorsoepitrochlearis and triceps brachii
351 muscles with a role in elbow extension. This index is identical to the index of fossorial ability
352 in some references (e.g., Hildebrand, 1985b). Ulnar robustness index (URI): expresses the
353 ability of ulna to resist against bending and shearing stresses as an indicator for robustness of
354 the ulna. It also shows relative area available for the origin and insertion of forearm and forefoot
355 (manus) muscles (flexors, pronators, and supinators). Manus proportions index (MANUS):
356 indicates relative proportion of proximal (third metacarpal bone) and distal (proximal phalange
357 of third digit) elements of the manus and size of the palmar surface. Crural index (CI): indicates
358 relative proportion of proximal (femur) and distal (tibia) elements of the hindlimb. Gluteal
359 index (GI): shows relative mechanical advantage of the gluteal muscle function, which is used
360 in retraction of the femur. Femoral robustness index (FRI): shows the ability of femur to resist
361 against bending and shearing stresses and indicates robustness of the femur. Femoral
362 epicondylar index (FEI): shows relative area which is available for the origins of the soleus and
363 gastrocnemius muscles which are used in extension of the knee and plantar flexion of the
364 hindfoot (pes). Tibial robustness index (TRI): shows the ability of tibia to resist against bending
365 and shearing stresses as an indicator of tibia robustness. Tibial spine index (TSI): expresses
366 relative mechanical advantage of the function of hamstrings and biceps femoris muscles across
367 the knee and hip joints. Pes length index (PES): shows relative proportion of proximal (femur)
368 and distal (metatarsal bone) elements of the hindlimb, and relative size of the hindfoot.
369 Intermembral index (IM): indicates the length of the forelimb relative to the hindlimb (Samuels
370 & Van Valkenburgh, 2008). Detailed descriptions of measurements are included in Tables 1
371 and 3, and Figure 14.

372 [Table 3]

373 **3. RESULTS**

374 **3.1. Postcranial morphology of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse**

375 **3.1.1. Vertebral column**

376 The total count of vertebrae in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is 56, comprised of 7 cervical, 12
377 thoracic, 5 lumbar, and 4 sacral vertebrae, followed by 28 caudal vertebrae.

378 The first cervical vertebra (atlas) has short and broad atlantal transverse process (ATTP) (Figure
379 1b). The two axial transverse processes (AXTP) create a hemi-arc towards each other in ventral
380 view of the second cervical vertebra (axis) (Figure 1g). Caudal extension of axial neural process
381 (AXNP) in lateral view of axis is little (Figure 1h). Shape of centrum of seventh vertebra (CC)
382 in rostral view looks oval, and transverse foramen (CTF) is circular in shape. The location of
383 carotid tubercle of the seventh cervical vertebra (CCT) towards the centrum makes a wide angle
384 (Figure 1p).

385 [Figure 1]

386 The first thoracic vertebra has well-developed transverse processes (TPZ) and
387 prezygapophyses (TPRZP) (Figure 2a) with a vertical neural spine (TNS) (Figure 2b).
388 Prezygapophyses of the second thoracic vertebra (Figure 2c) is obviously smaller as compared
389 to that of first thoracic vertebra and the shape of the neural spine tip of the second thoracic
390 vertebra in dorsal view is pitchfork (Figure 2d). The numerically mid-thoracic vertebrae
391 (thoracic vertebrae 6 and 7) are almost similar in shape (Figure 1h,i). Diaphragmatic vertebra
392 (= thoracic vertebra where the zygapophysal facet orientation changes) is thoracic vertebra 10.
393 Anticline vertebra (= thoracic vertebra where the orientation of the spinous processes changes)
394 is also thoracic vertebra 10 (Figure 2k).

395 [Figure 2]

399 The first and second lumbar vertebrae have small transverse processes (LTP) and
400 prezygapophyses (LPZ) (Figure 3a,b), while other lumbar vertebrae have longer transverse
401 processes and prezygapophyses (Figure 3e,g). The neural spines (LNS) are short in the first two
402 lumbar vertebrae, and the shape of the neural spine of the second lumbar vertebra in dorsal view
403 is almost robust (Figure 3b). Neural spine increases in length, and fifth lumbar vertebra shows
404 a large crest-like neural spine (Figure 3g).

405 The sacrum has a little curvature (Figure 3l). In rostral view, the shape of the prezygapophyses
406 of first sacral vertebra (SPZP) is lunate and the angle between them is close (Figure 3i). The
407 first and second sacral vertebrae have prominent transverse processes (= ala of sacrum) (STP)
408 with slightly wide lateral surfaces that are originally attached to the ilia (Figure 3j-l).
409 Intervertebral foramina (SIF) are big (Figure 3j,k). A small median crest (SMC) rises from the
410 ventral surface in the center of the four sacral vertebrae, the extent of the union of sacral
411 vertebrae 1-4 in ventral view is small, and vertebral discs are slightly visible (Figure 3k). There
412 is no connection between the neural spines of sacral vertebrae (Figure 3l).

413 [Figure 3]

414
415 Among the 28 caudal vertebrae, the first five are similar in length to the sacral vertebrae (Figure
416 4a-c). Starting with the sixth caudal vertebra (Figure 4d-f), the length of the vertebrae increases
417 abruptly. The transverse processes (CATP) of the first five caudal vertebrae are long, blade like,
418 and are partly divergent (Figure 4a-c). The second caudal vertebra has more elongated
419 transverse processes with more divergence (Figure 4c). The neural spines (CANS) of the first
420 two caudal vertebrae are completely grown (Figure 4a) and the prominent prezygapophyses
421 (CAPZP) are visible on the first and second caudal vertebrae (Figure 4a-c). Tail length in
422 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is longer than the head and body length. Maximum length is
423 reached almost in the middle of the tail length, at the twelfth caudal vertebra (Figure 4l) and
424 from this position and further distally, the vertebral length and width (or diameter) gradually
425 decrease, resulting in a series of long and thin succeeding tail vertebrae (Figure 4l-z").

426 [Figure 4]

427

428 3.1.2. Thoracic cage

429 Ribs are curved with a flattened shape at the distal end, which demarcates the transition to the
430 cartilaginous costal rib. The number of true, false and floating ribs are 7, 3, and 2, respectively.
431 Thus, the number of free ribs (= posteriocaudal ribs that do not directly articulate with the
432 sternum) are five. The first rib angle in rostral view is arched in shape. First rib lacks an accessory
433 uncus near the tubercle (FRT) in rostral view (Figure 5a).

434 General shape of the manubrium of sternum is short and slender (Figure 5b,c). Tip of the angle
435 of the jugular notch (JN) in the proximal part of the manubrium is completely flat (Figure 5b),
436 and ventral crest of manubrium is thin (Figure 5c).

437 [Figure 5]

438

439 3.1.3. Pectoral girdle

440 The clavicle shows slight curvature. The cross-section in the middle part of the clavicle is
441 almost round, while the medial end is flattened. The lateral facet, which articulates with the
442 acromion (= acromial end) (AE), is slightly flattened and broadened. The position of the
443 costoclavicular ligament at the sternal end (SE) of the clavicle is distinguishable (Figure 6a).

444 General shape of the scapula is short and slender; it doesn't have an obvious extension in the
445 corner of inferior ala, and the length of the scapula is almost 1.5 times longer than its width
446 (Figure 6b and Table 1). The scapular neck (SNK) is narrow and appears to be slightly twisted
447 against the scapular plate (Figure 6b,c), and a small posterior extension of the caudal angle
448 (SCA) can be observed (Figure 6b). The cranial and vertebral borders of scapula do not make

449 an angle. In dorsal view, the scapular spine (SS) extends almost to the vertebral margin of the
450 scapula, separating the supraspinous fossa (SSF) from the infraspinous fossa (ISF), which are
451 similar in size. However, relative length of infraspinous fossa is slightly more than that of the
452 supraspinous fossa (7 vs. 6 mm) (Figure 6b). Superior process of the scapula spine (SPSS) in
453 dorsal view is slightly significant. The acromion ramus (SAR) has been separated from the rest
454 of the spine in the 2/4 rostral of the length of scapula. In dorsal view, the acromion process of
455 the scapula (SAP) shows a curvature with an extended tip towards the rostral region. A well-
456 developed acromion process lies anterior to the coracoid process and does not extend beyond
457 it. The metacromion process is absent (Figure 6b). The coracoid process (SCP) is hook-like in
458 shape, and is straightly separated from the glenoid fossa. The shallow, small, and round glenoid
459 fossa (GF) of the scapula with a slightly thickened margin partially covers the humeral head
460 (Figure 6d).

461 [Figure 6]

462

463 **3.1.4. Forelimbs**

464 Humeral head (HH) is large and rounded in shape, clearly distinct from the shaft (= body), and
465 has a weak posterior projection (HPP) (Figure 7a,c). The diaphysis of the humerus is slender,
466 and the middle part of the humeral shaft shows an almost round cross-section. While the
467 proximal part of the humerus is expanded dorsoventrally, the distal part extends mediolaterally.
468 The lesser tubercle (LT) is located just medial to the humeral head and it is small and rounded
469 (Figure 7a). The greater tubercle (GT) is oval in shape and has an irregular surface but not very
470 well-developed (Figure 7a,c). The tubercles do not surpass the height of the humeral head. In
471 the caudal view and proximal part of the humerus, the relative height of the greater tuberosity
472 (in relation to the humeral head) is lower (Figure 7a). The deltoid tuberosity (= deltoid crest,
473 deltopectoral crest) (DT) is located in the proximal half portion of the diaphysis, and slightly
474 extends laterally with the rounded distal tip. The deltoid tuberosity is a thin blade structure that
475 forms a lunate towards the shaft of the humerus (Figure 7b). On the medial aspect of the
476 humerus, the distal part of a crest which origins from the anterior side of the humerus crosses
477 over to the medial side to connect to the bony bridge of the lateral epicondyle (LE) and forms
478 the lateral epicondylar crest (= supinator crest), which is well-developed (SC) (Figure 7a,b). In
479 the distal epiphysis, the capitulum (CA) is expanded and separated from the trochlea (TR) by
480 a shallow concave groove (G) associated with ulnar nerve (Figure 7a). The trochlea is flattened
481 mediolaterally. It is pulley-shaped, and its orientation with respect to the longitudinal axis of
482 the humerus is slightly oblique. Trochlea shows more distal extension as compared to the
483 capitulum (Figure 7b). The olecranon notch (ON) is quite deep, and the supratrochlear foramen
484 (STF) in the coronoid-olecranon notch (CON) is generally present, which gives an open shape
485 to the coronoid fossa (CF) in the distal portion of the humerus. Coronoid fossa is located above
486 the trochlea and capitulum and the place of articulation of the olecranon process in the elbow
487 joint (Figure 7a,b). There is a distinct lateral epicondyle developed in the specimens. The
488 medial epicondyle (ME) is pronounced but without any obvious tip, with a large tuberosity as
489 an attachment surface for the digital flexor muscles (Figure 7a). The radial fossa (RF) is present
490 and can be observed above the lateral epicondyle (Figure 7b). There is no entepicondylar
491 foramen in epiphysis zone of the humerus.

492 [Figure 7]

493

494 Ulna is the longest bone of the forelimb, with a slightly sigmoid curve (Figure 8a-c). The
495 olecranon process (UOP) is short and robust; it is slightly developed and defined by two small
496 crests: lateral olecranon crest (LOC) and medial olecranon crest (MOC) (Figure 8b). The shape
497 of the olecranon superior ridge of the ulna (OSR) is curved (Figure 8a). In caudomedial view,
498 the olecranon of the ulna (O) shows a significant (great) depression (Figure 8c). In the rostral

499 view of the proximal region of the ulna, the medial curvature of olecranon process is slightly
500 present, and the medial extension of the medial coronoid crest (MCC) is absent (Figure 8b).
501 The coronoid process (UCP) is well-developed medially and forms medial coronoid crest
502 (MCC), while the lateral coronoid crest (LCC) is less-developed (Figure 8b). The semi-lunar
503 notch (SN) is relatively open with a semi-circular shape, and almost large, relative to the size
504 of the olecranon (Figure 8a-c). The radial notch (RN), which serves as the articular facet for
505 radius, is wide and oblique (Figure 8b). The longitudinal groove (LG) is deep (Figure 8a). A
506 small tubercle, named as the tubercle of ulnar shaft (T) in Figure 8b, is present on the medial
507 edge of the ulnar body, connected to a longitudinal groove for muscles anconeus and abductor
508 pollicis longus. Ulnar tuberosity (UT) is weak and linear in shape (Figure 8c). The distal surface
509 of the ulna has a quadrangular outline and is smaller in size than the distal surface of the radius.
510 The styloid process (SPU) is rounded and well-developed and the carpal surface is crescent-
511 shaped and slightly concave (Figure 8b).
512 The shaft of the radius is slim and almost cylindrical with a flat side on the contact surface with
513 the ulna (Figure 8d,e). The proximal portion of the diaphysis is considerably curved. Generally,
514 the convex degree of the axis of the radius in medial view is large (Figure 8d). The proximal
515 end of the radius has an extended radial head (HR) and bears a small articular surface for ulna
516 (ASU) (Figure 8d) and a prominent elliptical articular surface (= central fossa) for the humeral
517 capitulum (ASHC) (Figure 8e). The radial tuberosity (RT) is well-developed (Figure 8d), and
518 there is a pronounced developed interosseous crest (= radial ridge) (RR), which extends distally
519 (Figure 8e). The styloid process (= radial distal malleolus) (SPR) is small (Figure 8e).

520 [Figure 8]

521
522 In manus (Figure 9a), metacarpal bones (MC) show only a very little curvature (Figure 9b-e).
523 The third (Figure 9d) and fourth (Figure 9c) metacarpals appear elongated and the third one is
524 the longest metacarpal bone, followed in order by the fourth, second (Figure 9e), fifth (Figure
525 9b) and first metacarpals. The metacarpal bones have a slender shaft and generally a round
526 cross-section in the mid-shaft. The distal end of the metacarpals is rounded and the trochlear
527 end with two condyles, which are separated by a groove (Figure 9b-e). The phalanges of digits
528 show little elongation and slight curvature. Those of the proximal row (PPH) (Figure 9f-i) are
529 all slightly convex dorsally. Although their proximal end is slightly concave and the width is
530 more expanded, the distal end of the proximal phalanges is rounded and appear to be slightly
531 trochlear with two small condyles separated by a very weak and shallow groove (Figure 9f-i).
532 The length of the proximal and intermediate (IPH) (Figure 9j-m) phalanges of digits are two
533 third of the length of the corresponding metacarpal and proximal phalange, respectively.
534 Proximal and distal ends of the intermediate phalanges are simpler than those of the proximal
535 phalanges, showing less expanded proximal ends and less trochlear morphology, respectively
536 (Figure 9f-m).

537 [Figure 9]

538 539 **3.1.5. Pelvic girdle**

540 The ilium is long and thin in most of the middle part and it contributes slightly more than 50%
541 to the length of the innominate bone (Figure 10a,b). Ilium shape is slightly curved at the rostral
542 end. Iliac wing (IW) does not form a large blade, and iliac crest (IC) is slightly developed.
543 While the cross-sectional outline of the ilium is almost oval in the middle parts of the bone, it
544 expanded and thickened in its proximal and distal parts. Acetabular notch (AN) is considered
545 open, because the acetabulum outline is incomplete, but it is shallow. The acetabulum outline
546 is not large. Shape of the contour of iliopectinal eminence (= pectineal tuberosity) (IE) is
547 curved, and anterior inferior iliac spine (AIIS) shows little protuberance (Figure 10a). The
548 pubis is long and slender. However, the proximal and distal margins of the pubis is slightly

549 rugose and weakly triangular in shape. Although, from distal end towards the proximal end,
550 the triangular shape of shaft almost disappears and thus, the cross-section of the most proximal
551 part of pubis shows very weak angles, almost displays a flattened oval. Shape of the pubis
552 tubercle (PT) in lateral view is picked, and the tip of the pubis angle (PA) is located almost in
553 front of the 1/3 inferior of the anterior arc of the obturator foramen (OF) and therefore, the
554 pubic symphysis (PS) is very short in length. Moreover, length of pubic symphysis as compared
555 with the distance between the tip of the pubis angle and iliopectinal eminence is greatly shorter,
556 also it is smaller in relation to the rostrocaudal size of the obturator foramen. The protuberance
557 of the tuberosity of ischium (IT) is small and it is weakly developed. In posterior direction, the
558 ischium becomes wide and flattened, but the dorsolateral border between the ischial tuberosity
559 and the acetabular part of the bone, known as the ischial spine (IS), becomes slender, but not
560 like the ilium (Figure 10a). Caudal portion of ischium body is curved a little bit laterally and
561 the shape of the ridge of the ischium body around the tuberosity is arced (Figure 10b). The
562 obturator foramen is large, and the posterior arc of the obturator foramen shows a triangular
563 posterior curvature (Figure 10a,b). Since the analyzed specimens were all males, dimorphism
564 was not detected in this region.

565 [Figure 10]

566

567 **3.1.6. Hindlimbs**

568 The femur in its overall morphology is long and slender with a straight and cylindrical diaphysis
569 (Figure 11a,b). The shaft widened distally towards the medial and lateral condyles. In the
570 proximal epiphysis, the femoral head (HFE) is spherical and dorsomedial oriented with a
571 relatively long neck (FN) (Figure 11a,b), which forms a wide angle (approximately 45°) to the
572 longitudinal axis of the femoral shaft. The coverage of the femoral head by the acetabular
573 articular surface is relatively shallow. The head bears a deep fovea capitis (FC) for the ligament
574 of the femoral head (Figure 11c). Femoral trochanteric fossa (FTF) is narrow (Figure 11b), and
575 its proximal margin is concave, separating the greater trochanter (GTR) from the femoral head
576 and its neck. The greater and lesser trochanters (LTR) are well-developed. The greater
577 trochanter extends dorsally above the femoral head. The lateral margin of the greater trochanter
578 (= anterior intertrochanteric crest) (ITC) is thickened and well-developed, and this thickened
579 margin merges with the shaft on the lateral side. There is no small uncus near the femoral greater
580 trochanter. The lesser trochanter is located almost at the base of the femoral neck. It is under-
581 developed and posteromedially oriented on the shaft of the femur. However, it is smaller than
582 the greater trochanter in size. The position of the lesser trochanter towards the femoral shaft
583 creates a lunate (Figure 11b). The third trochanter (TTR) is slender but well-developed and it
584 is located in the 1/3 of the proximal of the length of femoral shaft. In the distal end of the femur,
585 the two condyles are separated by the intercondylar fossa (ICF) on the caudal aspect of the
586 bone, which is narrow and deep. The two condyles have minor differences in shape and size
587 with each other; the lateral condyle (FLC) is slightly wider and bigger than the medial condyle
588 (FMC). The distal metaphysis in caudal view has a short ridge (R). The patella groove (=

589 trochlear groove for patella: TRGP) is almost deep (Figure 11a,b).

590 The tibia is longer than the femur and slightly thinner in shape (Figure 11d). It is the longest
591 bone of the hindlimb with a sigmoid curvature along its entire length. The diaphysis of the tibia
592 is almost round in cross-section in the mid part, just before the junction of the tibia and fibula.
593 The outline of the head of tibia (HT) in the proximal view is almost triangular to rectangular,
594 but the distal end is slightly compressed mediolaterally (Figure 11e). The tibial tuberosity (TT)
595 is developed and the tibial crest (TC) is anteriorly projected below the proximal condyles,
596 parallel to the tibial ridge (TRD). There is also a crest in the soleal line (SLC). The intercondylar
597 (= inter condyloid) area is narrow with an evident groove (IG). In the proximal part of the tibia,
598 the lateral condyle (TLC) is slightly more concave than the medial condyle (TMC), and the

599 medial condyle is flatter but smaller than the lateral condyle. The lateral malleolus (LM) on the
600 distal epiphysis is smaller and slightly longer than the medial malleolus (MM) (Figure 11d).
601 The fibula has a lunate head (HFI) and shows the proximal portion compressed and the distal
602 portion cylindrical (Figure 11d). The fibula is slightly shorter and thinner than the tibia and are
603 fused to each other in the half-proximal part, but almost in the middle of the tibia shaft.

604 [Figure 11]

605

606 Among the tarsal bones only calcaneus and astragalus (= talus) are preserved and other bones
607 are missed. Therefore, our analyses provide limited morphological information related to
608 posterior mesopodium.

609 The body (= corpus) of calcaneus is long and slender and the neck of the calcaneus is straight
610 (Figure 12a-c). On the dorsal view, the medial articular surface (middle facet for the astragalus)
611 (MAS) is an elongated oval, extending medially. The lateral articular surface (posterior facet
612 for the astragalus) (LAS) is a flat discoidal area. There is an accessory facet that extends
613 forward to the anterior border of the calcaneus, articulating with the anterior marginal facet of
614 the astragalus (anterior facet for the astragalus) (AFA) (Figure 12a). The posterior end of the
615 calcaneus is expanded into a knob-like structure, forms a short and simple calcaneal tuberosity
616 (CT) (Figure 12b). The groove for the tendon of flexor hallucis longus muscle (GT) is deep
617 (Figure 12c). The cuboid articular surface (CAS) in anterior view of calcaneus is mostly oval
618 rather than round (width: 0.82, length: 1.03) and is obliquely oriented (Table 1 and Figure 12d).
619 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse has a relatively large astragalus (Figure 12e). The astragalus has
620 a well-defined astragalar globular head (AH) and long neck (N). It is approximately half of the
621 size of the calcaneus, with a size ratio 43% (2.02 vs. 4.68 mm) (Table 1 and Figure 12e). The
622 trochlea is asymmetrical and wide. Both malleolar surfaces are flat. The medial malleolar
623 surface (MMS), ends almost at the base of the neck and does not surpass the margin of the
624 head, while the lateral malleolar surface (LMS) is much longer, and extends slightly over the
625 neck. This gives a pot-shape to the body of astragalus with larger lateral surface as compared
626 to medial surface. The width of the trochlea is more than its length. The dorsal articular surface
627 is continued posteriorly over the posterior process, and the arc of the trochlea is thereby
628 increased (TA). In ventral view, just behind the trochlea, there is a relatively deep groove (=
629 sulcus of astragalus) (ST) for the flexor hallucis longus tendon (Figure 12e).

630 [Figure 12]

631

632 The metatarsal bones (MT) of pes (Figure 13a) are slender and elongated with very little
633 curvature (Figure 13b-f). The first metatarsal bone is obviously shorter (Figure 13f), but the
634 others are of comparable length and size (Figure 13b-e). The second and third metatarsal bones
635 (Figure 13e,d, respectively) are sub-equal in length and are the longest metatarsal bones,
636 followed in order by the fourth (Figure 13c), fifth (Figure 13b) and first (Figure 13f) metatarsal
637 bones. The metatarsal bones have round cross-sections in the mid-shaft. Each metatarsal bone
638 shows a slightly grooved palmar aspect. While the proximal joints are concave in shape
639 (especially for metatarsal bones 1 and 2) and expanded, the distal joints of the metatarsal bones
640 consist of two small condyles separated by a shallow groove. Proximal phalange of digits (PPH)
641 (Figure 13g-k) have little curvature, are slightly rounded in distal ends, and have a trochlear
642 shape with two small condyles separated by a weak groove, but their proximal ends are more
643 expanded and concave. The length of the proximal phalanges is slightly more than one third of
644 the length of the corresponding metatarsal bones, while that of the intermediate phalanges (IPH)
645 (Figure 13l-o) is approximately two third of the length of the proximal phalanges. The
646 intermediate phalanges are similar to the proximal ones, but smaller and with less curvature;
647 the proximal end is slightly expanded, while condyles are present in distal end, and the groove
648 in-between is shallow, showing a trochlear morphology. In the terminal phalanges (TPH) (e.g.,

649 Figure 13p) the dorsal aspect of the core of phalange shows vertical crests in both proximal and
650 distal ends, resulting in a curved dorsal margin, but the ventral margin shows a very weak
651 convex.

652 [Figure 13]

653

654 Evaluation of postcranial morphological characters in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse following
655 the list of characters and character polarity (presented in Table 2) reveals that 53 characters out
656 of 86 (61.6%) show an ancestral character state, while 27 characters out of 86 (31.3%) indicate
657 a derived character state. The rest of the six characters (6.9%) show an intermediate polarity.

658

659 **3.2. Postcranial measurements of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse**

660 Ratios of length to width of eight postcranial bones, including sacrum, last lumbar vertebra,
661 scapula, humerus, ulna, innominate bone, femur, and tibia were calculated for brown rat,
662 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, great gerbil, Persian jird, small five-toed jerboa, and steppe field
663 mouse (Table 1) according to the illustrations presented in Figure 14. Bivariate diagrams of
664 length and width were provided in Figure 15.

665 The ratio of length to width of sacral bone for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is 1.93, while the
666 lowest and highest ratios are for small five-toed jerboa (1.57) and brown rat (2.32), respectively
667 (data for steppe field mouse was missed) (Figure 15a). The ratio of length to width of last
668 lumbar vertebra for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is 0.89. Steppe field mouse shows the
669 minimum (0.57) and Persian jird has the maximum (1.59) ratios among all six examined species
670 (Figure 15b). The value of the length of scapula to its width is 1.63 for Goodwin's brush-tailed
671 mouse, with the lowest ratio for great gerbil (1.14) and the highest ratio for the Persian jird
672 (1.81) (data for small five-toed jerboa was missed) (Figure 15c). The ratio of length to width of
673 humerus for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is 14, which is the highest value among other
674 species, while the lowest ratio is for small five-toed jerboa (0.93) (data for steppe field mouse
675 was missed) (Figure 15d). The ratio of length to width of ulna for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse
676 is 20, which is the highest value, equal to that of the Persian jird. In contrast, great gerbil showed
677 the minimum ratio (8.33) (data for steppe field mouse and small five-toed jerboa were missed)
678 (Figure 15e). The value of the length of innominate bone to its width is 2.67 for Goodwin's
679 brush-tailed mouse, with the lowest ratio for small five-toed jerboa (2.01) and the highest ratio
680 for steppe field mouse (3.5) among all six species (Figure 15f). The ratio of length to width of
681 femur for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is 16.11, which is the highest value, and the lowest
682 ratio is for brown rat (8.85) (data for steppe field mouse was missed) (Figure 15g). The value
683 of the length of tibia to its width is 15.24 for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, which is the lowest
684 value, and the highest ratio is for small five-toed jerboa (17.5) (data for steppe field mouse and
685 great gerbil were missed) (Figure 15h).

686

[Figures 14, 15]

687

688 Scaling plots of 15 morpho-functional indices of fore and hindlimbs for 22 species were shown
689 in Figures 16-18. Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse shows the same or close values of URI, GI,
690 and TSI to those of terrestrial, saltatorial and fossorial species, respectively (Figures 16f, 17b,
691 18b), considering at least one species out of the three included species for each locomotory
692 group. It also displays close values for: OLI to two terrestrial and one semi-aquatic species
693 (Figure 16e), TRI to the all species within the terrestrial and arboreal groups (2 species for each
694 category), and to one of the three semi-aquatic species as well (Figures 18a), and SMI to the
695 three saltatorial species and only one of the semi-aquatic species as well (Figures 16a).
696 Moreover, the species is also close in the value of HEB to one aerial and one semi-aquatic
697 species (Figure 16d). On the other hand, with regards to the FEI, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse
698 possesses a value similar to that of both terrestrial and saltatorial groups equally regarding to

699 the number of included species (only one species) (Figures 17d). For BI, HRI, and FRI, the
700 species has similar values to those of the aerial species (Figures 16b,c, 17c), and for CI and
701 PES, it can be considered similar to semi-aquatic species group in the values (Figures 17a, 18c).
702 With regards to the IM, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse shows similarities to a mixed group of
703 arboreal, saltatorial, terrestrial, and semi-aquatic species (Figures 18d).

704 [Figures 16-18]

705

706 **4. DISCUSSION**

707 This study provides a detailed description of the postcranial elements of a species of brush-
708 tailed mice following examination of several qualitative and quantitative traits of the axial and
709 appendicular skeletons. We mapped morphological characteristics of the postcranium of
710 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse and attempted to match morphological specializations with
711 information on the ecology and behavior of the species, and also provided a primary database
712 for phylogenetic inferences.

713

714 **4.1. Shape variations and functional adaptation of postcranium**

715 In the following section, some of the eco-morphological traits and morpho-functional
716 characterizations of postcranium in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse are discussed following a
717 short summary of morpho-functional features of each bone according to the previous published
718 literature.

719

720 **4.1.1. Vertebral column**

721 Evolution of the vertebral column and the shape of vertebrae are influenced by several factors
722 including size, allometric limitations, serial homology (integration between vertebrae),
723 phylogenetic constraints, ecological specializations and adaptation to diverse ecological niches
724 (Slijper, 1946; Arnold et al., 2016). Since the axial skeleton has a crucial role in body support
725 and movement, facilitating respiration, and anchoring the head and limbs, it is subject to
726 selection for a variety of functional and ecological specializations (Bramble & Carrier, 1983;
727 Rawls & Fisher, 2010; Arnold et al., 2017). In mammals, the vertebral column is not
728 homogenous: it shows morphological variations resulting in discrete regions. However, the
729 vertebral column of mammals is constrained with regards to the vertebral count (Narita &
730 Kuratani, 2005; Asher et al., 2011).

731 In the region of cervical vertebrae, the laterally expanded transverse processes of atlas along
732 with the posteriorly extended neural process of axis suggest powerful neck flexors and a good
733 ability to rotate the head (Argot, 2003; Carrizo et al., 2014). The trunk vertebrae of mammals
734 are classified into thoracic and lumbar regions. Most tetrapod species show lateral bending of
735 their trunk during locomotion, while sagittal bending can be observed in mammals when
736 leaping and jumping or during asymmetric gaits (e.g., galloping, bounding) (Schilling &
737 Hackert, 2006; Harty, 2010). This specialized mobility of the vertebral column is associated
738 with the evolution of a ribless lumbar region: sagittal movements in mammals are restricted to
739 the posterior trunk, and the presence of zygapophyses with vertical orientation in this region
740 facilitates these motions (Schilling & Hackert, 2006). Variations correspond to locomotor
741 ecology and behaviors were focused in the lumbar region (e.g., posture, gliding, climbing,
742 running, jumping, swimming, and hunting behavior). Hence, there is a known strong correlation
743 between lumbar morphology and ecology, which reflects the important role of the lumbar
744 region in mammalian locomotion (Alvarez et al., 2013; Randau et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2018).
745 Moreover, an increase in the rate of morphological disparity and evolution of the posterior trunk
746 has been reported in mammals; they display highly differentiated thoracolumbar region. This
747 suggests that natural selection for locomotion plays an important role in rapid morphological
748 evolution of thoracic and lumbar trunk regions, and subsequently the acquisition of new and

749 diverse morphologies (Jones et al., 2018). The long, robust and well-developed lumbar neural
750 processes reflect powerful extensor muscles in lumbar region, which may be related to the
751 weight of trunk (Argot, 2003; Martin, 2005; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009; Carrizo et al., 2014). In
752 lumbar vertebrae, laterally developed transverse processes, with deeper cranial and caudal
753 notches and anteriorly directed tips, increase the areas of attachment of lumbar flexors and
754 extensor muscles, allow the mechanical advantage of these muscles (e.g., sacrospinalis and
755 quadratus lumborum muscles), and enable greater bending (flexion and extension movements)
756 of the spine (Gambaryan, 1974; Alexander & Jayes, 1981). In swift mammals, flat and wide
757 lumbar transverse processes (especially at their lateral margins) along with robust and forward-
758 directed spinous processes, reduce the range of movements. This can be associated with an
759 increased elastic storage of energy in relevant ligaments (Gambaryan, 1974; Biewener &
760 Blickhan, 1988). In contrast, in slow runners, like rodents, relatively reduced-size of transverse
761 and spinous processes and wide articular processes suggest little lumbar mobility (Álvarez et
762 al., 2013).

763 Trunk vertebrae of mammals can be divided according to the width and inclination of the
764 spinous processes into regions anterior and posterior to the anticline vertebra. Posteriorly
765 located spinous processes allow flexion and rotation and avoid mechanical interferences. In
766 contrast, spinous processes which are robust and forward-directed, increase the area for
767 ligament attachment, and reduce flexion, extension and rotation (Álvarez et al., 2013).
768 Furthermore, based on the orientation of the zygapophyseal articular surfaces, trunk vertebrae
769 can be grouped into pre and postdiaphragmatic vertebrae (Slijper, 1946; Gambaryan, 1974;
770 Boszczyk et al., 2001). The diaphragmatic region (or the diaphragmatic vertebra) has a great
771 role for the axes of movement along the vertebral column. In prediaphragmatic part, the
772 zygapophyseal facets show more or less horizontal orientation; this allows lateral bending and
773 tilting movements but restricts sagittal bending in the anterior trunk. Controversially, in the
774 postdiaphragmatic region, the zygapophyseal facets of trunk vertebrae are more upright and
775 located in an almost parasagittal plane; this permits sagittal bending but restricts lateral bending
776 or tilting in the posterior trunk (Slijper, 1946). The size of the zygapophyseal articular surface
777 also reflects the amount of intervertebral joint movements (Fick, 1911). In the tail region, the
778 transverse processes of caudal vertebrae, which formed broad lateral wings, indicate the well-
779 developed basal musculature of the tail. Moreover, the neural canals, which are still detectable
780 on more proximal caudal vertebrae, play an important role in the innervation of the tail (Argot,
781 2003; Carrizo et al., 2014).

782 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, because of short and broad atlantal transverse processes and
783 little extension of axial neural process, it seems that neck flexor muscles are not powerful. Both
784 diaphragmatic and anticline vertebrae are situated at thoracic vertebra 10, which means that the
785 change of the orientation of the zygapophyseal facet and the spinous process provide a wide
786 region of sagittal bending movements (flexions and extensions) in the caudal part of thoracic
787 region and the posterior trunk. This species has well-developed neural processes of lumbar
788 vertebrae which means possessing strong lumbar extensor muscles. Except the first and second
789 lumbar vertebrae, the rest of vertebrae in lumbar region have relatively well-developed
790 transverse and spinous processes, showing a good function of lumbar flexors and extensors,
791 and thus, good lumbar mobility as a non-swift small mammal. The sacral region consists of a
792 single element, with no indication of the additional fusion which is seen in many fossorial
793 animals as reported by Dunn & Rasmussen (2007). With extended transverse processes of the
794 first five caudal vertebrae, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is expected to have well-developed
795 basal musculature of the base of the tail and a good innervation of tail. The first six caudal
796 vertebrae exhibit long zygapophyses. It is interpreted that a mobile articulation is present at the
797 postzygapophyses of each of these six caudal vertebrae and the prezygapophyses connected to
798 it caudally.

799

800 **4.1.2. Thoracic cage**

801 Jenkins (1970) stated that thickened ribs might facilitate slow climbing and bridging in
802 subfamily Lorisinae, a group of primates, by increasing the stability of the thorax and the
803 vertebral column. The elongated thoracic vertebrae with more numbers of wide ribs is also an
804 advantageous in bats, helping them to hang (Szalay & Lucas, 1993; Simmons & Quinn, 1994;
805 Simmons, 1995; Szalay & Lucas, 1996) and/or for stability of the thorax during flight (Slijper,
806 1946). The manubrium of sternum with a well-developed ventral crest is an indicator of
807 pectoralis strength (Argot, 2003; Martin, 2005).

808 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, the ribs are slender without any obvious robustness; although
809 for the first rib, the length of the neck is slightly more than the half of the shaft length (1.3 vs.
810 2.1 mm), for the rest of the ribs, the neck length is less than the half of the shaft length, which
811 gives a long and slender appearance to the rib cage, without any particular functional
812 specialization. With a thin ventral crest in manubrium, a weak pectoralis muscle is expected for
813 the species.

814

815 **4.1.3. Pectoral girdle**

816 The elbow joint is considered as one of the best indicators of habitat choice (in the case of
817 substrate selection), and locomotion behavior in mammals. Its morphology can reflect the
818 relation between mobility and stability, and the extent of pressure transmission resulted by the
819 body weight on the forelimbs. The elbow joint has an important function in the rotation of the
820 forelimb in pronation and supination, a motion important for mammals which may need to
821 retain this ability to a certain extent for food manipulation (Figueirido et al., 2016).

822 The scapula is a bone with a complex morphological structure in mammals that plays a major
823 role in their locomotion. Morphology of scapula can reflect the response to the influence of
824 functional and phylogenetic factors (Morgan, 2008). Moreover, body size can also influence
825 scapular morphology through special biomechanical requirements. The functional requirements
826 include scapular mobility and shoulder stabilization, as essential components of mammal's
827 locomotion (Fischer et al., 2002; Morgan, 2008). In arboreal species, having a short scapula
828 would bring the center of body mass closer to the substrate, which is important for maintaining
829 balance during climbing (Schmidt & Fischer, 2011). However, in fossorial species of similar
830 body size, in which jumping is less important, very short scapula can facilitate locomotion in
831 narrow tunnels under the ground (Stein, 2000). A ventral prolongation of the vertebral border
832 of the scapula, which is associated with the origin of the teres major muscle in subterranean
833 rodents, is often enlarged in scratch diggers to provide a greater area of origin and greater lever
834 arm for the flexor muscle of the shoulder. In contrast, this posterior angle of the scapula is
835 generally small and less-developed in terrestrial rodents (Fernández et al., 2000, Lessa et al.,
836 2008).

837 Resistance to the tensile forces in the shoulder region, is partially related to the development of
838 the infraspinous fossa and partly to the robustness of the scapular neck (Argot, 2003; Martin,
839 2005; Seckel & Janis, 2008; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009). The infraspinatus muscle acts as an arm
840 retractor during vertical climbing in sciuriform rodents (Wölfer et al., 2019). On the other
841 hand, the supraspinatus muscle is an elevator and protractor of the arm (Larson & Stern, 1986).
842 It plays a role in fast protraction of the arm during vertical climbing, and stabilizing the shoulder
843 joint during arm powerful retractions when climbing (Argot, 2001). For example, a larger
844 supraspinous fossa in arboreal sciuriforms as compared to aerial sciuriform rodents
845 indicates that the second group includes less agile climbers (Wölfer et al., 2019). The
846 acromiodeltoid muscle protracts and lifts the arm, and is attached to the acromion process
847 (Salton & Sargis, 2008). A robust acromion process which has an increased attachment site for
848 the acromial part of the deltoid muscle means better ability of the scapula to stabilize the

849 shoulder joint during aerial locomotion (Wölfer et al., 2019). The muscles which are attached
850 to the metacromion (atlantoscapularis ventralis, spinodeltoid, and trapezius) (Thorington et al.,
851 1997) are involved in scapular stabilization and humeral rotation. Therefore, possessing a
852 prominent metacromion is an indicator for heavy loading at the shoulder region. A developed
853 metacromion is more associated to aerial locomotion, less related to arboreal and the least
854 linked to fossorial locomotions (Salton & Sargis, 2008; Wölfer et al., 2019).
855 Development of the scapular spine and extension of the coracoid process limit the lateral
856 movements of the forelimb (Martin, 2005; Seckel & Janis, 2008). The robustness of the
857 coracoid process is considered as an indicator showing the need to stabilize the position of
858 scapula, mostly in aerial and less in fossorial species. A more robust coracoid process increases
859 the adductor forces created by the coracobrachialis and short biceps muscles; these forces help
860 vertical climbing on trees and have role for maintaining balance on slender and inclined
861 substrates (Essner & Scheibe, 2002). However, digging or terrestrial species do not require such
862 large adductor forces (Argot, 2001; Sargis, 2002). The broad clavicular articulation restricts
863 extensive rostrocaudal excursions of the scapula along the thoracic cage and stabilizes the
864 shoulder joint during gliding in aerial species. However, these stabilizing roles are less relevant
865 for climbers, and least relevant for diggers and terrestrial species (Wölfer et al., 2019).
866 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse a short scapula helps to maintain balance of the animal during
867 climbing and jumping. There is little resistance to the tensile forces due to the slight
868 development of the infraspinous fossa and low robustness of the scapular neck, but there should
869 be a good lateral movement of the forelimb due to the development of the scapular spine and
870 straight extension of the coracoid process. There is also a small caudal prolongation of the
871 vertebral border of the scapula which has developed weakly. This can be associated with the
872 scratch digging habit of the species. Although the species lacks any metacromion process, but
873 a robust acromion process has a role in scapular stabilization and humeral rotation. The shallow
874 and small clavicular articulation has less role in stabilizing the shoulder joint during climbing,
875 but it can facilitate the movements of the forelimb during terrestrial locomotion and scratch
876 digging.

877

878 **4.1.4. Forelimbs**

879 The forelimb of rodents has been the subject of several studies in functional morphology (e.g.,
880 Candela & Picasso, 2008; Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Coutinho et al., 2013; Samuels
881 et al., 2013; Carrizo et al., 2014; Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017; Wölfer et al., 2019). It has
882 different functions; forelimb supports the body weight in most terrestrial species, assists in
883 maintaining balance and grasping in arboreal species, has an important role in flying and
884 landing in gliding species, helps fossorial species in scratching and digging, and also to loosen
885 and shovel away soil, provides propulsion and helps aquatic species in swimming (Socha et
886 al., 2015; Wölfer et al., 2019).

887 In general, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, as an epigeous species, has longer and thinner bones
888 as compared to the digging species, as for example discussed in Samuels & Van Valkenburgh
889 (2008). In this species, which is sometimes found living in small dispersed colonies and is more
890 likely to have a large home range in the habitats with scattered vegetation, elongation of limb
891 bones may equip the animal with ability to be cursorial and saltatorial for foraging and find
892 suitable habitat, as well as the ability to move fast and run away from predators in areas with
893 less plant cover and shelters for hiding.

894 The mammal's humerus is a major component of the forelimb skeleton. Morphological traits
895 and variations in the humeral shape are also associated with the evolutionary history, particular
896 locomotory habits, and substrate preferences (functional specializations) (Morgan & Álvarez,
897 2013). The robustness of the humerus can also be reflected by the quotient anteroposterior width
898 at mid-shaft/total length of humerus (Fernández et al., 2000). Analysis of locomotor adaptations

899 in rodents showed that a shorter and more robust humerus with a well-developed deltoid
900 tuberosity, which has extended more towards distal section, and a broad and well-developed
901 distal epiphysis and muscular attachment sites may reflect the wide functional spectrum of the
902 species, including running, digging, and even swimming habits (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh,
903 2008; Morgan & Álvarez, 2013). However, runner species tend to have longer, gracile humerus
904 with narrow distal epiphysis (Morgan & Álvarez, 2013).

905 It has been also demonstrated that the shape of the humeral head can vary with locomotion
906 behavior (Argot, 2001; Sargis, 2002; Salton & Sargis, 2008). Arboreal mammals, including
907 most arboreal sigmodontine rodents, as well as terrestrial and semi-aquatic sigmodontines but
908 with low frequency, tend to have a more rounded humeral head. This increases the range of the
909 rotational movements of the humerus in all directions (Argot, 2001; Carrizo et al., 2014;
910 Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017). On the other hand, well-developed humeral tubercles are
911 considered as indicators which reflect powerful stabilizing shoulder muscles to withstand the
912 forces applied across the elbow joint during digging (Argot, 2001; Sargis, 2002). In addition,
913 the large greater tuberosity of the humerus, which restricts the range of shoulder movements to
914 the parasagittal plane, is a characteristic of cursorial species (Polly, 2007; Salton & Sargis,
915 2008). The supraspinatus and infraspinatus muscles (suprascapular muscular group) insert in
916 the greater tuberosity, whereas subscapularis muscle (latissimus-subscapular muscular group)
917 attaches to the lesser tuberosity (McEvoy, 1982). The relative height of the greater tuberosity
918 in most arboreal, scansorial and saltatorial sigmodontines is lower or the same height in relation
919 to the humeral head, with the first being more frequent. This condition can be considered as a
920 good indicator of arboreal habits in arboreal mammals, such as rodents and marsupials (Szalay
921 & Sargis, 2001; Sargis, 2002; Rose & Chinnery, 2004; Candela & Picasso, 2008). However,
922 semi-fossorial and semi-aquatic sigmodontines showing the higher condition (Coutinho & de
923 Oliveira, 2017). A lower greater tuberosity allows movements in the glenohumeral joint which
924 is required for climbing (Candela & Picasso, 2008). The three mentioned muscles are rotator-
925 cuff muscles which have roles in the motions of the shoulder joint. The supraspinatus muscle
926 acts as a protractor and abductor of the humerus on arrival movements, the infraspinatus muscle
927 abducts and externally rotates the humerus during climbing, and the subscapularis muscle
928 medially rotates the humerus and maintains the integrity of the shoulder joint (McEvoy, 1982).
929 These muscles will have a larger inserting area when the greater tuberosity is lower (Sargis,
930 2002), which will provide a greater integrity to the shoulder joint during the climbing
931 movements (McEvoy, 1982).

932 The deltoid crest in humerus is the site of insertion for two groups of muscles of the forearm:
933 pectoralis minor and major muscles (pectoral muscular group) and clavodeltoideus and
934 acromiodeltoideus muscles (deltoid muscular group) (McEvoy, 1982). The first three muscles
935 have a synergistic role in adduction and internal rotations of the humerus, assist to place the
936 distal part of the forelimbs into a medial position when the elbow is flexed (McEvoy, 1982).
937 The last muscle, acromiodeltoideus, participates in protraction and abduction movements of
938 the forelimbs. More powerful forces can be provided by the forelimbs with increasing the
939 insertion area for these four muscles, which is crucial for the movements in the scansorial,
940 digging, and swimming (McEvoy, 1982; Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008). Coutinho & de
941 Oliveira (2017) also stated that all semi-fossorial, most semi-aquatic and scansorial, and some
942 terrestrial and arboreal species of sigmodontine rodents presented a thick and globular shape
943 of the deltoid crest of the humerus. More resistance to the loads imposed by muscular action
944 and substrate resistance during scratch digging is provided by the greater robustness of the
945 deltoid tuberosity (Stein, 2000). A well-developed deltoid crest with great distal extension (i.e.
946 distance from muscle attachment to joint) enhances mechanical advantage by increasing out-
947 forces exerted by the deltoid and pectoralis muscles that contribute to forelimb retraction
948 (Fernández et al., 2000; Stein, 2000; Morgan & Álvarez, 2013). In contrast, the proximally

949 located deltoid crest optimizes speed over force production, as expected for cursorial forms
950 (Polly, 2007).

951 The perforated olecranon fossa (notch) in the humerus may have a role in increasing the range
952 of muscle extension in the humeroulnar joint (Argot, 2003; Martin, 2005; Kuncová & Frynta,
953 2009; Carrizo et al., 2014). A closed olecranon fossa has been observed in arboreal
954 sigmodontines; it is associated to the relatively movable elbow joint during extension of the
955 forearm and prevents a complete extension of the ulna (Argot, 2001; Szalay & Sargis, 2001;
956 Sargis, 2002; Candela & Picasso, 2008; Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017), while in the other
957 locomotion modes (aerial, fossorial, and terrestrial) mostly the olecranon fossa is open
958 (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017). In addition, in the distal portion of the humerus, the medial
959 epicondyle is the origin site of carpal and digital flexors and pronator muscles of the forearm
960 (pronator teres and flexor carpi radialis), and the lateral epicondyle is the origin of carpal
961 extensors and supinator muscles (McEvoy, 1982; Lessa et al., 2008). In both digging and
962 scansorial taxa, a larger humerus width across epicondyles can provide a broader area of origin
963 for these muscles, and more powerful flexion of the wrist and digits during scratch digging, and
964 ensuring a strong grasp during climbing. This character was expressed as a ratio relative to the
965 total length of the humerus (Argot, 2001; Sargis, 2002; Morgan & Álvarez, 2013). Furthermore,
966 separation of trochlea and capitulum with a shallow concave groove shows that a little pressure
967 is constrained to the elbow joint (Argot, 2003).

968 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, as a species with fast terrestrial movements and a high
969 proportion of activity on the ground, humerus is a long and gracile bone, with a narrow distal
970 epiphyses. The humeral robustness index (HRI) is 0.07 (Table 3), showing no considerable
971 robustness of the humerus as compared to semi-aquatic, arboreal, semi-fossorial, fossorial and
972 saltatorial rodents (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008) (also see Table 3 for comparison). In
973 the following sections, this morpho-functional index will be discussed in more details. The ratio
974 of humerus width across epicondyles/total length of the humerus is 0.25 (Table 1), which
975 locates in the range of index mentioned by Dunn & Rasmussen (2007) for terrestrial rodents
976 (0.166-0.303). This can be considered as an indicator of the less mechanical strength of the
977 carpal and digital muscles in comparison with digger species, showing a range of index value
978 of 0.288-0.40. Rodents with digging ability have a mediolaterally broader distal humerus
979 relative to humeral length that can be used as an index that separates fossorial rodents from all
980 other groups (Dunn & Rasmussen, 2007). Have a smaller ratio, the species cannot provide a
981 powerful flexion of the wrist and digits during scratch digging, ensuring a strong fossoriality.
982 In this species, similar to the generalized and scansorial taxa, the humeral tuberosities never
983 surpass the level of the humeral head, thus allowing a wide range of shoulder movements. A
984 small greater tuberosity facilitates good rotational movements of the humerus in different
985 directions. However, the absence of well-developed humeral tubercles indicates that the species
986 does not have powerful stabilizing shoulder muscles to withstand the forces applied across the
987 elbow joint which are needed during digging. The relative height of the greater tuberosity is
988 lower in relation to the humeral head, allowing movements in the glenohumeral joint which are
989 required for climbing.

990 Notably, in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, the deltoid tuberosity showed an intermediate
991 position between non-subterranean and subterranean taxa (proximally extended deltoid
992 tuberosity), which demonstrated less mechanical strength that the corresponding muscles can
993 produce, as compared with those of the diggers. The deltoid tuberosity is mostly slender,
994 forming a thin blade rather than displays a thick and globular shape. Absence of a robust deltoid
995 tuberosity means that the species is unable to provide resistance against substrate forces during
996 digging. Hence, only a scratch digging activity may be expected. The proximally located deltoid
997 tuberosity also gives fast running ability to the species. On the other hand, an open coronoid
998 fossa which is observed in the species, allows a complete extension of the ulna and increases

999 the stability of the elbow joint during extension of the forearm. A shallow concave groove,
1000 which separated the trochlea and capitulum, shows that a little pressure is constrained to the
1001 elbow joint.

1002 In mammals, ulna shows a similar trend to humerus in the structure. The olecranon process of
1003 the ulna is the site of origin and insertion of several muscles of the forearm, such as triceps and
1004 dorsoepitrochlearis, digital, and carpal flexor muscles. This character is relevant to the total
1005 length of the ulna and reflects the mechanical advantage of forearm muscles (Fernández et al.,
1006 2000). In scratch diggers, these muscles are well-developed, in which out-forces exerted by the
1007 claws contribute to breaking the soil. The curvature of the olecranon process of ulna, determines
1008 the line of action of carpal and digital flexor muscles (Vassallo, 1998). In the anterior view of
1009 the proximal region of the ulna, the medial curvature of olecranon process is the origin region
1010 for the flexor carpi ulnaris muscle (flexor muscular group of the forearm) and the insertion site
1011 for the triceps brachii caput medialis and longus muscles (triceps muscular group) (McEvoy,
1012 1982). Greater effective forces for muscles, which originate in the olecranon and in the medial
1013 epicondyle of the humerus, will be provided by a greater ulnar curvature (Vassallo, 1998;
1014 Fernández et al., 2000; Lessa et al., 2008). In most semi-fossorial and some terrestrial and semi-
1015 aquatic sigmodontines, the medial curvature is present (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017). This
1016 pattern was also observed in other semi-fossorial mammals (Vassallo, 1998; Lessa et al., 2008).
1017 The humeral trochlea locates in the greater sigmoid cavity and acts like a pivot during the
1018 movements of the elbow joint. Therefore, the presence of the mesial extension of the greater
1019 sigmoid cavity in the proximal part of the ulna associates with the safety of the elbow joint
1020 (Flores, 2009). This is important in diggers due to the strong extension of the shoulder and
1021 elbow joint (Vassallo, 1998) and in the semi-aquatic rodents which need to overcome water
1022 resistance (Stein, 1988). Coutinho & de Oliveira (2017) observed a higher frequency of this
1023 cavity in semi-aquatic and semi-fossorial sigmodontine rodents, whereas a lower frequency in
1024 arboreal, terrestrial, and scansorial sigmodontines was reported. The longitudinal groove in the
1025 lateral view of the ulna, is the origin site for the extensor carpi ulnaris muscle (extensor
1026 muscular group of the forearm) and the insertion point of anconeus muscle (triceps muscular
1027 group). Hence, a deeper groove may indicate the higher power of these muscles (McEvoy,
1028 1982).

1029 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, the olecranon process of ulna is not well developed to
1030 produce enough forces to break the soil, and the ratio of the length of the olecranon process/total
1031 length of the ulna in this species, as a species not able to excavate in hard soils, is 0.10 (Table
1032 1). Dunn & Rasmussen (2007) mentioned that the range of this index for terrestrial rodents is
1033 0.182-0.355 and for fossorial species, it is 0.227-0.305. Therefore, this ratio in Goodwin's
1034 brush-tailed mouse is less than that of diggers. Thus, only a scratch digging may be expected
1035 for the species. This rodent possesses a slightly sigmoid curved ulna, showing a small degree
1036 of medial curvature of the olecranon process. This means that digital and carpal flexor muscles
1037 can produce only weak effective forces. The medial extension of the medial coronoid crest is
1038 absent, which means that stabilizing the movements of the elbow joint is not essential because
1039 no real digging occurs. This again can be an indicator of having only a scratch digging.
1040 However, the longitudinal groove is deep, which provides a good site for the forearm extensor
1041 and triceps muscular group.

1042 In terrestrial forms of mammals (at least in placentals), the head of radius tends to be more oval
1043 in shape (or even rectangular in mediolateral direction) and shallower, which reflects restriction
1044 of the elbow rotation through allowing pronation and supination. In contrast, in arboreal forms,
1045 the head of the radius is round and circular in shape and relatively deep, which reflects the
1046 spherical nature of the capitulum of humerus, and facilitates this motion (MacLeod & Rose,
1047 1993). In scansorial taxa the radial head shows an intermediate morphology, but more like
1048 arboreal group. Although a rounded radial head is not essential for supination, but this motion

1049 is facilitated when the curvature of the radial head abutting the ulnar surface is more convex
1050 rather than flat (Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020). For example, the African spring hare (family
1051 Pedetidae) is a bipedal semi-fossorial saltatorial rodent. It has a completely round radial head
1052 which gives the ability to the animal to use its forelimbs exclusively for manipulation of food
1053 items and for burrowing (Kingdon, 1974).

1054 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, the extended radial head, which is oval in shape, bears a small
1055 articular surface for ulna. There is a prominent elliptical articular surface (= central fossa) for
1056 the humeral capitulum. Hence, allowing for rotation of the elbow to permit pronation, while
1057 supination is restricted.

1058 Since grasping is important for small mammals who do climbing, the manual digits and claws
1059 of arboreal rodents are relatively elongated, which facilitate and improve grasping and
1060 capturing the prey (Hildebrand, 1978; Van Valkenburgh, 1987; Samuels & Van Valkenburgh,
1061 2008). Arboreal rodents have shorter metacarpal bones relative to humerus length and have
1062 longer manual phalanges relative to the length of the third metacarpal bone (Dunn &
1063 Rasmussen, 2007). Gliding rodents (aerial category) have relatively equal proportioned limbs
1064 and equal manual and pedal claw lengths, similar to the arboreal group (Samuels & Van
1065 Valkenburgh, 2008). Semi-fossorial and fossorial rodents displayed relatively elongated claws
1066 on the manus (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008); elongated terminal phalanges with fast-
1067 growing manual claws are used in breakdown of the soil (Hildebrand, 1985b; Stein, 2000). In
1068 addition, other than the claws and pisiform, which is the insertion of the manual flexors, the
1069 manual bones of fossorial rodents are extremely reduced. This distal shortening, reduces the
1070 out-lever and improves the mechanical advantage of muscles playing roles during digging
1071 (Stein, 2000; Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008). Moreover, the rounded distal ends of the
1072 metacarpal bones are considered to be a characteristic of increasing the rotation and the
1073 abductor musculature of the digits (Kümmell, 2009).

1074 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, the manual digits and claws are relatively elongated which
1075 facilitate grasping rocky surfaces during climbing. In this study, the value of MANUS for this
1076 species is 0.66, which is even slightly more than the mean value for all terrestrial (0.624),
1077 saltatorial (0.617), semi-fossorial (0.578), fossorial (0.524) and semi-aquatic (0.573) species
1078 included in the study of Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008) (Table 3, Figure 16g). Distal ends
1079 of the metacarpals are rounded which helps to have a good movement of the digits. This species
1080 shows only a scratch digging activity, which is characterized by the alternate extension and
1081 flexion of the forelimbs. In this digging mode, the claws of the manus and pes are used to break
1082 up and loosen the soil superficially (Tulli et al., 2016).

1083

1084 **4.1.5. Pelvic girdle**

1085 Because of to the rigid connection of the innominate bone to the vertebral column, the iliosacral
1086 joint has restricted movements (Fischer et al., 2002). In symmetrical gaits (e.g., walking and
1087 trotting), back movements include rotational motions around the rostrocaudal body axis (=
1088 tilting) and lateral motions in the horizontal plane (= lateral bending). While in asymmetrical
1089 gaits, spinal motion is restricted to dorsoventral flexions and extensions in the sagittal plane
1090 (Jenkins & Camazine, 1977; Schilling & Hackert, 2006). The shape of the innominate bone
1091 shows great variations among species, which can be related to variables such as phylogeny and
1092 gaits, or simply to a lack of selection. This highlights how informative the morphology of this
1093 bone is. For instance, most ambulatory species show an open acetabulum, moderate to short
1094 pubic symphysis and ischiopubic complex, and a moderate to elongated ilium which suggest a
1095 generalized condition with moderate or weak propulsion of the hindlimbs and a wide range of
1096 possible movements of the hip (Álvarez et al., 2013). Elongated ischium increases the mass
1097 and the mechanical advantage of the hamstring muscle group (strong hip extensors) and some
1098 other extensor muscles, and elongated ilium increases that of the knee extensor and gluteal

1099 muscle group (weak hip extensor musculature, secondarily abductor). Elongated pubic
1100 symphysis and well-developed pectineal line increase the mass and the mechanical advantage
1101 of adductors and stabilizers of the hip (Álvarez et al., 2013).
1102 An elongated ischium and pubic symphysis in fast species help them to reach higher running
1103 speeds and high-power output to accelerate and control their direction. However, the slower
1104 taxa, showed a wide range of innominate bone shapes, from extremely well-developed ischium
1105 and pubic symphysis, and reduced ilium to extremely short ischium and pubic symphysis, and
1106 elongated ilium (Williams et al., 2007; Álvarez et al., 2013). Among slower taxa, boulder
1107 species such as rodents, show marked adaptations to jumping: they share an elongated ilium
1108 and ischium and a well-developed pectineal line. This is related to the great amount of energy
1109 which is needed at the hip and knee joints for supporting and moving the body upward with
1110 the hindlimbs pushing together during the propulsive phase of bounding gaits (Gambaryan,
1111 1974; Hildebrand, 1988b; García-Esponda & Candela, 2010). These mammals can run with
1112 several changes in direction and acceleration, and frequently may use bounding gaits (Williams
1113 et al., 2007). The presence of a moderate or elongated pubic symphysis, and a well-developed
1114 pectineal tuberosity (= iliopectinal eminence), is related to a marked hip extension and
1115 stabilization during bounds and rapid changes of direction in running (Williamset al., 2007).
1116 Slow running diminishes the need for strong hip stabilization. A relatively open acetabulum
1117 and weak pectineal tuberosity suggest the wide range and independent excursion of the limbs
1118 (relative to the hip) during galloping (as compared with bounding), while a closed acetabulum
1119 can be related to mechanical stabilization of the hip joint during hopping (Jenkins & Camazine,
1120 1977; Polly, 2007). An extremely reduced ischium body and pubic symphysis, elongated ilium,
1121 high ischiopubic complex, forward-directed ischial tuberosity, and open acetabulum, similar to
1122 what can be observed in e.g., hedgehogs, are the traits showing a rapid movement but weak hip
1123 extensor and abductor muscles (Jenkins & Camazine, 1977). Elongated ilium and ischiopubic
1124 complex which can be observed in saltatorial taxa are linked to strong propulsion of the body
1125 and stabilization of the hip (Smith & Savage, 1956; Jenkins & Camazine, 1977). Cursorial
1126 species share some features such as elongated ilium, wide vertical ramus of the ischium, and a
1127 reduced pectineal tuberosity which are linked with both rapid and powerful hip extensor
1128 muscles that provide the possibility of reaching and sustaining fast running (Álvarez et al.,
1129 2013). The broad iliac crests, which are expanded in the frontal plane, may be partially related
1130 to the width of the trunk and the development of the epaxial musculature (Argot, 2003; Martin,
1131 2005; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009). A rugose tuberosity on the dorsal margin of the ischium, just
1132 posterior to the acetabulum, provides a well attachment site for the corresponding muscles and
1133 for example, can suggest a strong pull exerted by the ischiocaudalis muscle (Argot, 2003).
1134 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, although the presence of an elongated ilium, a relatively
1135 slender ischium and a well-developed pectineal tuberosity are indicators of jumping ability, but
1136 the species lacks elongated pubic symphysis and closed acetabulum, indicating that the
1137 mechanical stabilization of the hip joint during jumping and rapid movements is not very strong.
1138 Furthermore, the iliac crest is slightly broad, which shows the good development of the epaxial
1139 musculature, but with a little protuberance of the ischial tuberosity, the pulling strength of the
1140 ischiocaudalis muscle should be weak in this species.

1141 1142 **4.1.6. Hindlimbs**

1143 The shape of the femur shows changes which are related to body mass. For example, larger
1144 taxa display a more robust femoral neck, major development of the trochanteric fossa and a
1145 well-developed greater trochanter with an increase of muscular mass and mechanical advantage
1146 of hip extensor and abductor muscles (Argot, 2002; Fisher et al., 2008). The reduction and/or
1147 caudal orientation of the lesser trochanter in larger species suggest restricted rotation and
1148 movements out of the parasagittal plane (Argot, 2002; Heinrich & Houde, 2006). On the other

1149 hand, the femoral configuration is one of the most obvious features of the femoral head related
1150 to limb posture and excursion, which is considered as a structural adaptation. For instance,
1151 Jenkins & Camazine (1977) stated that in raccoons and bears, which are ambulatory and
1152 noncursorial species, the anterior margin of femoral articular surface extends across the femoral
1153 neck proximally, toward the greater trochanter, and forms an angle with the femoral shaft at
1154 about 50°. It also extends posteriorly towards the intertrochanteric fossa. This orientation
1155 provides a surface for articular cartilage contact in a relatively abducted posture of the femur
1156 and for further limb abduction in other activities such as climbing. Moreover, a relatively
1157 shallow coverage of the femoral head by the acetabular articular surface facilitates greater
1158 femoral excursions and movements, especially abduction and rotation, than those used in
1159 walking, which are essential for climbing and clambering over uneven and disordered
1160 substrates (Jenkins & Camazine, 1977). Some saltatorial sigmodontines have a spherical
1161 femoral head; this accentuates the abduction range of the femur and assists in the action of the
1162 hindfeet when jumping. A more spherical head has been reported in some arboreal, terrestrial,
1163 and semi-fossorial sigmodontines (Argot, 2002; Carrizo et al., 2014; Coutinho & de Oliveira,
1164 2017). While the lesser trochanter of femur serves as the attachment site for muscles that
1165 protract/adduct the hindlimb, the third trochanter is the attachment site for retractor/abductor
1166 muscles (Wölfer et al., 2019). Prominent lesser and third trochanters suggest the presence of
1167 relatively large muscles, which can create tensile forces (Scheidt et al., 2019). In the anterior
1168 view of the proximal region of the femur, the lesser trochanter can form a projection from the
1169 margin of the femur. This region is the insertion site for the iliacus and psoas major muscles
1170 (iliacus muscular group) (McEvoy, 1982). Coutinho & de Oliveira (2017) reported a medial
1171 orientation of the lesser trochanter of the femur observed among arboreal sigmodontines. This
1172 projection increases the external rotation, flexion, and protraction functions of the femur by the
1173 iliacus and psoas major muscles, improves climbing ability and helps the leg to move forward
1174 on arboreal substrates (McEvoy, 1982; Argot, 2002; Candela & Picasso, 2008). It is reported
1175 that in the fossorial group, the lesser trochanter is located more distal along the midshaft
1176 (Wölfer et al., 2019).

1177 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, as a small-sized rodent, as expected, the femoral neck is not
1178 robust and the trochanteric fossa is narrow. However, the lesser and greater trochanter are well-
1179 developed, which indicate the presence of tensile forces. A posteromedially orientation of the
1180 lesser trochanter on the shaft of femur, increases the external rotation and protract/adduct
1181 functions of the bone, which improve climbing activity. In contrast to fossorial rodents, the
1182 lesser trochanter in this species is located more proximal along the midshaft, which shows less
1183 ability of the species to dig burrows. Displaying a spherical femoral head and a relatively
1184 shallow coverage of the femoral head by the acetabular articular surface facilitate limb
1185 abduction and femoral movements when jumping and climbing over disordered rocky
1186 substrates.

1187 Among mammals, swifter taxa and bounders, including lagomorphs and many rodents, share
1188 many traits in the morphology of tibia related to a typically crouched posture. They have a
1189 moderate to high anterior location of the tibial tuberosity, which allows strong extension of the
1190 knee and promotes the propulsion and acceleration of the body (Gambaryan, 1974). They
1191 possess a sub-equally sized articular condyles, and a wide lateral condyle which is related to
1192 the importance of the transmission of body mass to the lateral condyle and the degree of fusion
1193 between tibia and fibula. In many rodents, the tibia and fibula are fused at the level of the
1194 medial shaft, as an adaptation to swift jumps (Barnett & Napier, 1953; Hildebrand, 1988b).
1195 However, most ambulatory mammals share rounded and anteroposteriorly short condyles, with
1196 a more or less ample lateral condyle, in association with a wide range of movements out of the
1197 parasagittal plane (Álvarez et al., 2013). Cursorial species with wide home ranges, that travel
1198 long distances, share a wide cranial intercondyloid area and anteriorly located base of the tibial

1199 tuberosity, which favor strong extension of the knee when the hindlimb is extended (Álvarez
1200 et al., 2013). In the posterior view of the tibia, the presence of a crest in the soleal line provides
1201 an attachment site for muscles of the flexor group of the leg (insertion area for the popliteus
1202 muscle and origin site for the tibialis posterior and digitorum tibialis muscles) (McEvoy, 1982).
1203 In semi-fossorial sigmodontines, this crest can be absent (a very rare condition), developed
1204 crest-like shape (which exhibits a higher frequency), or showing an under-developed state (with
1205 lower frequency). Since digging tends to push the body backwards as soil resists, having a
1206 greater development of the three mentioned muscles ensures a strong flexion of the leg and
1207 maintains a stable position (Samuels, 2007). Arboreal, scansorial, and very few terrestrial
1208 sigmodontines, present (or even lack) an under-developed crest in the soleal line of the tibia,
1209 which limits the insertion area for the flexors of the leg, and results in a more tenuous action
1210 of the three muscles in these locomotion modes (Rose & Chinnery, 2004; Coutinho & de
1211 Oliveira, 2017).

1212 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, the fibula and tibia are fused at the level of the medial shaft,
1213 as an adaptation to fast jumps. The presence of a well-developed crest in the soleal line,
1214 facilitates the function of the flexors of the leg. A narrow cranial intercondyloid area
1215 demonstrates weak extension of the knee and hindlimb, while short rounded lateral and medial
1216 condyles allow a wide range of movements in the wrist joint.

1217 Within orders or families of placental mammals (Youlatos, 2003; Polly & MacLeod, 2008;
1218 Panciroli et al., 2017) and marsupials (Bassavora et al., 2009; Den Boer et al., 2019) it has been
1219 reported that the morphology of calcaneus and astragalus are good indicators of locomotory
1220 behavior. However, Janis & Martín-Serra (2020) stated that they could not discover a good
1221 functional locomotor signal for these tarsal bones across different orders of mammals.

1222 In jumping and cursorial taxa, the shape of the calcaneus and the neck is straight, and the body
1223 is usually long and rather narrow. The cuboid articular surface is oblique, crescent or bean-
1224 shaped. Therefore, these species favor parasagittal motions instead of transverse movements
1225 (Candela & Picasso, 2008; Ginot et al., 2016). In terrestrial rodents, calcaneus has a robust
1226 shape and does not display a marked lengthening. In semi-fossorial species, the neck of the
1227 calcaneus is more robust which bears well-marked muscular insertion areas. This is linked to
1228 the power of the lever arm of the foot, which is crucial in digging (Ginot et al., 2016).

1229 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, the straight shape of the calcaneus (and the neck), with a long
1230 and slender body (controversy to most terrestrial rodents) make it similar to that of jumpers and
1231 cursorial rodents, although the cuboid articular surface is oval rather than crescent or bean-
1232 shaped. These features give the ability of jumping and fast running to the species.

1233 Among mammals, in jumping and cursorial taxa, the trochlea of the astragalus is almost
1234 symmetrical and transversally compressed, which result in parasagittal movement of foot when
1235 rotated. The trochlear groove is deeper, which restricts the transverse movement when the foot
1236 is dorsally or plantarly flexed (Carrano, 1997; Candela & Picasso, 2008), avoiding injuries at
1237 the ankle (Hildebrand, 1985a; Hildebrand & Goslow, 2001). The astragalar neck is longer in
1238 jumping taxa, and shorter in cursors, but in both groups the neck is barely or not deflected
1239 medially. In terrestrial taxa, the head of astragalus is projected laterally and shows a round
1240 shape. The trochlea is rather symmetrical and has a deep groove (Ginot et al., 2016). The semi-
1241 fossorial and arboreal taxa show a long and deflected astragalar neck and an asymmetrical
1242 trochlea (Emry & Thorington, 1982). Fully subterranean species are characterized by a wide
1243 trochlea with a shallow groove, and a long astragalar neck with a spherical head, which help
1244 maintain the animal while digging and/or throwing the soil away (Carrano, 1997; Hildebrand,
1245 1985b; Davidovits, 2012).

1246 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, an astragalus with a relatively deep groove in ventral view,
1247 just behind the trochlea, restricts the transverse movement of the foot and makes it similar to
1248 that of jumpers, cursorial and terrestrial rodents, while possessing an asymmetrical trochlea

1249 (which is broader than longer), and a long neck are considered as shared features with semi-
1250 fossorial and arboreal taxa. A round and well-defined head, similar to what is observed in
1251 fossorial rodents, helps in stability of the animal while scratch digging.

1252 In many mammals, elongation of metatarsal bones is significant indicators of cursoriality.
1253 Furthermore, in saltatorial rodents, feet have elongated metatarsals and they are characterized
1254 with a high PES (Weisbecker & Schmid, 2007; Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Seckel &
1255 Janis, 2008). Moreover, one of the adaptations on limbs, which is associated with fast terrestrial
1256 movement is elongation of metatarsal bones (Elissamburu & Vizcaíno, 2004). The enlarged
1257 distal hindfeet of semi-aquatic rodents increases the length of the paddling limb and the size of
1258 the paddle as well. This will subsequently increase propulsive forces produced during
1259 swimming (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008).

1260 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, elongated autopodium facilitates jumping and fast
1261 movements. The value of PES for this rodent is 0.67, which is more than the mean value for
1262 all terrestrial (0.504), semi-aquatic (0.573), arboreal (0.355), semi-fossorial (0.411), fossorial
1263 (0.361) and aerial (0.327) species, but less than the mean value for saltatorial (0.876) group
1264 included in the study of Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008) (Table 3, Figure 18c).

1265

1266 **4.2. Postcranial morphology and phylogenetic inferences**

1267 Herein, we tried to provide almost a comprehensive list of postcranial characters through
1268 bibliography (and those which could be detected and examined in our specimens of Goodwin's
1269 brush-tailed mouse). More than the half of the characters (61.6%) showed plesiomorphic state,
1270 31.3% indicate apomorphic state and 6.9% show an intermediate polarity in the morphological
1271 evaluation of postcranium. The results further indicated the basal radiation of *Calomyscus*
1272 among other Muroidea. However, phylogenetic analyses are necessary to evaluate a complete
1273 set of characters, recognize informative and valuable character states, indicate characters
1274 showing convergent, divergent, or parallel evolution, reveal adaptation processes, and conclude
1275 a precise phylogenetic inference.

1276

1277 **4.3. Locomotory style in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse**

1278 Several studies have recorded the association between variations of postcranial anatomy and
1279 locomotion in mammals, including rodents (e.g., Polly, 2007; Morgan, 2008; Samuels & Van
1280 Valkenburgh, 2008; Hopkins & Davis, 2009; Alvarez et al., 2013; Carrizo et al., 2014; Carvalho
1281 Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017; Santana et al., 2019; Scheidt et al., 2019; Wölfer et al., 2019)
1282 based on morphological traits, comparative descriptions, and/or quantitative methods.
1283 Generally, due to the small size of small mammals and their more generalized overall anatomy,
1284 their postcranial is often considered to be uninformative for their locomotor behavior and mode
1285 of locomotion (e.g., Biewener, 1990; Christiansen, 1999; Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020).

1286 Terrestrial small mammals show differences in morphology of the limbs considering their
1287 different locomotor mode as compared to the other small mammals (arboreal, aerial, scansorial,
1288 saltatorial, and fossorial taxa) (e.g., Vassallo, 1998; Elissamburu & Vizcaíno, 2004; Hopkins &
1289 Davis, 2009; Pérez et al., 2017; Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020). They have an ovoid humeral head
1290 with small greater and lesser tubercles in proximal humerus, a large square capitulum with a
1291 capitular tail, and a shorter trochlea with a strong medial edge and distal projection in distal
1292 humerus (Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020). Their proximal ulna has a developed olecranon process,
1293 and a less prominent and sloping coronoid process, with a more constrained semi-lunar notch,
1294 and straight posterior borders. The proximal radius is oval or even rectangular in the
1295 mediolateral direction (Janis & Martín-Serra, 2020). A long femoral neck, a large greater
1296 trochanter with a smaller lesser trochanter in proximal femur, a long and narrow deep
1297 intercondylar groove, and a deep patella groove in the distal femur can be also observed (Janis
1298 & Martín-Serra, 2020). Moreover, a more prominent tibial tuberosity and a deeper intercondylar

1299 groove in proximal tibia are postcranial indicators for terrestrial small mammals (Janis &
1300 Martín-Serra, 2020). Generally, the extended forelimb of terrestrial species is better for
1301 propulsion along the ground (Szalay & Sargis, 2001; Sargis, 2002). Long distal elements of the
1302 hindlimb are also among important characters for species who inhabit open microhabitats (e.g.,
1303 Elissamburu & Vizcaíno, 2004; Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009).
1304 A loose hip joint with a high degree of lateral movement of the hindlimb is interpreted as a
1305 functional adaptation for climbing (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Kuncová & Frynta,
1306 2009).

1307 On the other hand, burrowing is a common activity among small mammals, even in those
1308 species that inhabit strict epigeous habitats. It is considered a highly energetic activity in order
1309 to produce considerable forces during excavation. Due to this activity, several physiological
1310 and anatomical changes can be found in the myoskeletal system of diggers (Luna & Antinuchi,
1311 2007). Digging species have shorter and thicker long bones than epigeous species (Lessa et al.,
1312 2008; Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Seckel & Janis, 2008). Relatively short ears and
1313 tails, robust ulna, stout ilium, and short and robust tibia are considered typical characters likely
1314 associated with the burrowing mode of life. The opposite is true for the rock-dwelling
1315 (petricolous) non-burrowing species (Kuncová & Frynta, 2009); the long tail (with balance and
1316 support function), long length of lumbar vertebrae, and long tibia have crucial roles when
1317 moving in rocky environments (including vertical jumping) (Kuncová & Frynta, 2009). While
1318 short lumbar part of the vertebral column participates in soil removal from burrow in
1319 subterranean species and helps the animal to brace the body against tunnel walls, long lumbar
1320 part of spinal axis is an adaptation on vertebral column which is associated with arboreal
1321 activity and fast terrestrial movement (e.g., Davis, 1964; Cartmill, 1985; Hildebrand, 1985b;
1322 Stein, 2000; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009; Jones et al., 2018).

1323 In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, possessing a relatively long lumbar vertebrae (Table 1), an
1324 ovoid humeral head, small greater and lesser tubercles which do not surpass the humeral head,
1325 a large square capitulum with a capitular tail, a short trochlea with a strong medial edge and
1326 distal projection, a well separation (deep groove) between the capitulum and the trochlea of
1327 humerus, a developed olecranon process of ulna, a less prominent and sloping coronoid process,
1328 a more constrained semi-lunar notch and straight posterior borders, a wide and slightly concave
1329 articular surface of the radial notch in ulna, an oval shape of the head of radius, a relatively
1330 short post-acetabular part in the innominate bone, a caudal shift of acetabulum, a long neck of
1331 femur, a large greater trochanter which extends above the femoral head with a short distal
1332 extension, a smaller lesser trochanter (as compared to the greater trochanter), an asymmetry
1333 between the lateral and medial condyles (with the lateral wider), a long and narrow deep
1334 intercondylar groove and a deep patella groove in distal part of femur, a long tibia with a
1335 prominent tibial tuberosity and a deep intercondylar groove, long metatarsal bones, and long
1336 tail are adaptations which are associated with fast terrestrial movements (including running and
1337 jumping) and the ecological habits (using above-ground nests in habitats with scattered
1338 vegetation). In Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, fast running or even leaping movements on long
1339 hindlimbs are used when traveling rapidly in open microhabitats. Relatively long distal
1340 elements of the fore and hindlimbs can be also linked with climbing activity in this species.

1341 The highest length of whiskers in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse was 39 mm, which is
1342 considered long as compared with other muroid rodents. For example, the mean length of
1343 whiskers for brown rat is 21 mm, for Southern mole vole (*Ellobius fuscocapillus* (Blyth, 1843))
1344 is 26 mm, in steppe field mouse is 27 mm, in short-tailed bandicoot rat (*Nesokia indica* (Gray,
1345 1830)) is 30 mm, for house mouse (*Mus musculus* Linnaeus, 1758) is 34 mm, and for Persian
1346 jird is 41 mm. The length of vibrissae is supposed to be functionally related to the width of
1347 investigated space; it is expected that the rock-dwelling species usually have extremely long
1348 vibrissae, while those of subterranean species are generally short (Table 1 and author's

1349 observations). Subsequently, it seems that only simple burrows, which consist of a slight
1350 alteration or superficial excavation of pre-existing crevices, hollows, or natural refuges, can be
1351 hypothesized for Goodwin's brush-tailed mice, used mainly as their shelters (Figure 19).

1352 [Figure 19]

1353
1354 Among the morpho-functional indices which were evaluated, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse
1355 shows the same value of ulnar robustness index as the Persian jird (known as a terrestrial
1356 species) (URI= 0.05) (Table 3, Figure 16f). According to Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008),
1357 mean value of URI for terrestrial group is 0.043 which shows a significant difference with that
1358 of aerial (0.021), semi-fossorial (0.055), fossorial (0.067) and semi-aquatic (0.057) groups, but
1359 is close to the value of arboreal (0.046) and saltatorial (0.045) groups. This index is an indicator
1360 for the resistance of the ulna against bending and shearing stresses (Samuels & Van
1361 Valkenburgh, 2008). Greater amount of URI in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse as compared to
1362 the mean value of URI for terrestrial group shows the robustness of ulna, more area available
1363 for the origin and insertion of relevant muscles, and hence, good functions of forearm and
1364 manus flexors, pronators, and supinators.

1365 This species also shows the same value of gluteal index to the small five-toed jerboa (known
1366 as a saltatorial species) (GI= 0.08) (Table 3, Figure 17b). Mean value of GI for saltatorial group
1367 is 0.115 which shows significant difference with those of aerial (0.071) and terrestrial (0.092)
1368 groups in analyses of Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008). Other groups show different values
1369 as follows: 0.119 in semi-aquatic, 0.112 in arboreal, 0.116 in semi-fossorial, and 0.125 in
1370 fossorial species (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008). In the present study, the value of GI for
1371 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is closer to the mean value of GI for aerial and terrestrial
1372 locomotory groups, rather than to that of the saltatorial group. Since this index shows the
1373 importance of the mechanical function of the gluteal muscles in retraction of the femur
1374 (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008), in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse it is not high enough
1375 to give the ability of high ricochet movements to the species, as compared to members of
1376 saltatorial group. Herein, lower value of GI in the examined small five-toed jerboa as compared
1377 to the mean value mentioned by Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008) may show a bias due to
1378 the insufficient specimens of the dipodid species (n= 1).

1379 The value of tibial spine index (TSI) for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is 0.49 which is
1380 comparable to those of the fossorial group (TSIs= 0.514, 0.513 and 0.507 for the three selected
1381 fossorial species) (Table 3, Figure 18b). Mean value of TSI for fossorial group is 0.452 which
1382 shows a significant difference with that of aerial (0.312), terrestrial (0.395), saltatorial (0.254),
1383 and semi-fossorial (0.378) groups, while in semi-aquatic and arboreal groups it is 0.443 and
1384 0.416, respectively (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008). Herein, the value of TSI for
1385 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is in the range of the value for fossorial group. With regards to
1386 the function of the biceps femoris muscle and the posterior thigh muscles (located between the
1387 hip and the knees) indicating by this index (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008), Goodwin's
1388 brush-tailed mouse benefits from mechanical advantage of these muscles for the movement of
1389 hindfeet.

1390 Moreover, the species shows very close amount of brachial index to the Palawan flying squirrel
1391 (*Hylopetes nigripes* (Thomas, 1893)) which is an aerial species (BI= 1.07 vs. 1.052,
1392 respectively) (Table 3, Figure 16b). As stated by Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008) mean
1393 value of BI for aerial group is 1.056 which shows a significant difference with those of arboreal
1394 (0.930), saltatorial (1.245), fossorial (0.908), and semi-fossorial (0.921) groups, while this
1395 index is 0.996 for terrestrial and 1.057 for semi-aquatic rodents. The study of Dunn &
1396 Rasmussen (2007) on several extinct and extant rodents showed that the range of this index for
1397 arboreal species is 0.811-1.03, for terrestrial species is 0.704-0.965, and for fossorial species is
1398 0.93-1.113. Hence, the relative proportions of proximal and distal elements of the forelimb for

1399 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is slightly more than the range of the index for terrestrial species,
1400 but is comparable to that of aerial, fossorial and semi-aquatic groups.
1401 The brush tailed mouse is also very close to the Northern flying squirrel (*Glaucomys sabrinus*
1402 (Shaw, 1801)) and Palawan flying squirrel, two aerial species, in the value of humeral
1403 robustness index (HRI= 0.07 vs. 0.064 and 0.066, respectively) (Table 3, Figure 16c). Mean
1404 value of HRI for aerial group is 0.062 which shows a significant difference with those of
1405 arboreal (0.094), terrestrial (0.086), saltatorial (0.094), fossorial (0.112), semi-fossorial
1406 (0.095), and semi-aquatic (0.105) groups as mentioned by Samuels & Van Valkenburgh
1407 (2008). Herein, the value of HRI for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is between the range for
1408 aerial and terrestrial groups. Since this index indicates robustness of the humerus (Samuels &
1409 Van Valkenburgh, 2008), the low amount of HRI in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse as
1410 compared to that of arboreal, saltatorial, fossorial, semi-fossorial and semi-aquatic species
1411 shows less ability of the humerus of this species to resist bending and shearing stresses.
1412 Moreover, the value of femoral robustness index of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is
1413 comparable to that of the three selected species for the aerial group (FRI= 0.06 vs. 0.056, 0.058,
1414 and 0.064) (Table 3, Figure 17c). Mean value of FRI for aerial group is 0.059 which shows a
1415 significant difference with those of arboreal (0.087), terrestrial (0.084), saltatorial (0.079),
1416 fossorial (0.104), semi-fossorial (0.086), and semi-aquatic (0.105) groups (Samuels & Van
1417 Valkenburgh, 2008). Herein, the value of HRI for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse shows
1418 congruence to that of aerial group but shows difference with the mean value of FRI determined
1419 for terrestrial species in the study of Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008). The lower amount
1420 of this index in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse as compared to terrestrial, arboreal, saltatorial,
1421 fossorial, semi-fossorial and semi-aquatic species indicates that the robustness of the femur and
1422 its ability to resist against bending and shearing stresses are less.
1423 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse shows a similar value of crural index to the South American
1424 water rat (*Nectomys squamipes* (Brants, 1827)) which belongs to the semi-aquatic group (CI=
1425 1.30 vs. 1.251, respectively) (Table 3, Figure 17a). Mean value of CI for semi-aquatic group is
1426 1.339 which shows a significant difference with those of aerial (1.129), arboreal (1.069),
1427 terrestrial (1.192), saltatorial (1.524), fossorial (1.054) and semi-fossorial (1.089) groups
1428 (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008). The study of Dunn & Rasmussen (2007) on several
1429 extinct and extant rodents showed that the range of this index for arboreal species is 0.941-
1430 1.056, for terrestrial species is 0.899-1.187, and for fossorial species is 1.022-1.329. Herein,
1431 the value of CI for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, which shows greater similarity to that of the
1432 semi-aquatic species rather than the terrestrial group, and also locates in the range of index
1433 determined for the fossorial group, indicates higher relative proportions of proximal (femur)
1434 and distal (tibia) elements of the hindlimb.
1435 In the present study, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse also shows the closest value of pes length
1436 index to two semi-aquatic rodents, South American water rat and African wading rat (*Colomys*
1437 *goslingi* Thomas & Wroughton, 1907) (PES= 0.67 vs. 0.607 and 0.787, respectively) (Table 3,
1438 Figure 18c). According to the study of Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008), the mean value of
1439 PES for semi-aquatic group is 0.573 which shows significant difference with those of aerial
1440 (0.327), arboreal (0.355), saltatorial (0.876), fossorial (0.361) and semi-fossorial (0.411)
1441 groups, while it is 0.504 for terrestrial group. Herein, the value of PES for Goodwin's brush-
1442 tailed mouse shows closest value to semi-aquatic group followed by terrestrial category. This
1443 index which is the ratio of length of the distal (metatarsal bone) to proximal (femur) elements
1444 of the hindlimb, shows the relative size of the hindfoot (Samuels & Van Valkenburgh, 2008).
1445 Other indices are more or less similar to the species belonging to different locomotion
1446 categories.

1447

1448

4.4. Posterior mesopodium of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse

1449 Two of the main bones of posterior mesopodium are calcaneus and astragalus. Study of Ginot
1450 et al. (2016) showed that cursorial and jumping taxa have high values of total length of
1451 calcaneus (CTL), but low values of total width of calcaneus (CTW) and width of cuboid
1452 articular surface (CCW). In these groups, the body of calcaneus is usually long and rather
1453 narrow. This means that these taxa favor parasagittal motions instead of transverse movements.
1454 Arboreal climbers, semi-fossorial and fossorial taxa are characterized by high values of CTW,
1455 CCW and height of cuboid articular surface (CCH), which has an elliptical shape allowing a
1456 variety of movements of the foot, through the cuboid. Semi-aquatic and generalist (= terrestrial)
1457 taxa have medium values. Because of the low values of cuboid articular surface (CCW and
1458 CCH), which is more slender, with a transverse compression, and a narrower facet, transverse
1459 movements of the foot in semi-aquatic and terrestrial species are generally more limited.
1460 Furthermore, the study of Ginot et al. (2016) revealed that while jumping, fossorial and semi-
1461 fossorial taxa have the highest values of calcaneal tuberosity width (TWC), generalists,
1462 cursorial and semi-aquatic taxa have intermediate values, and all of them show a rather robust
1463 calcaneal tuberosity. In contrast, arboreal climbers have a very low TWC value due to their
1464 more slender tuber. Moreover, the calcaneus neck width (NW) has the lowest value in climber
1465 taxa, which is linked to the curvature of the neck in these species. Cursorial taxa display an
1466 intermediate value, while other categories have higher values, showing a more robust neck
1467 shape (Ginot et al., 2016).

1468 We compared the mean value of several calcaneal variables of three terrestrial species,
1469 including Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, Persian jird and brown rat to the corresponding
1470 values of great gerbil as a semi-fossorial rodent. Measurements are included in Table 1. The
1471 mean values of CTW, CCW, CCH, and TWC for three examined terrestrial species were lower
1472 than those of great gerbil (CTW: 3.90 vs. 4.71, CCW: 1.73 vs. 3.12, CCH: 2.34 vs. 3.47, TWC:
1473 1.95 vs. 2.50), which is in congruence with the statements of Ginot et al. (2016). However, for
1474 CTL, the mean value for the first three species is 7.74, which is less than the CTL value for the
1475 great gerbil (8.82), controversially to what expected according to the study of Ginot et al.
1476 (2016), in which they showed that the value of CTL for fossorials is lower than that of
1477 terrestrials. This may be the effect of sample size on the analysis; only one specimen of great
1478 gerbil was examined. For NW, the mean value for the three terrestrial rodents was 1.53 and for
1479 the great gerbil the value was 1.97. Since we have no data for any other species belonging to
1480 other locomotory categories, making comparison is impossible. In general, in Goodwin's brush-
1481 tailed mouse, as a terrestrial rodent, because of the long and slender body of calcaneus and a
1482 slender cuboid articular surface which provides a narrower facet, transverse movements of the
1483 foot has been limited and the species favors parasagittal motions instead of transverse
1484 movements.

1485 In the study of Ginot et al. (2016) the astragalus total length (ATL) shows highest value in
1486 jumping and generalist taxa as compared to the other categories (climbers, fossorial, semi-
1487 fossorial, cursorial, semi-aquatic groups). This is because of the anteroposterior lengthening
1488 and a transversal compression of the bone. In contrast, semi-aquatic taxa have the lowest value
1489 due to the robust morphology of the astragalus. Generalist, climbers, fossorial and semi-
1490 fossorial taxa display the highest value of astragalus total width (ATW) due to their wide
1491 trochlea and medial projection of the neck. The lowest values are observed in cursors, jumpers,
1492 and semi-aquatic taxa, with a neck which is not laterally projected as much. The high value of
1493 astragalus body width (ABW) observed in semi-aquatic, fossorial, and semi-fossorial taxa, is
1494 linked to the lateral prominence of the ectal facet and width of trochlea, respectively. On the
1495 other hand, climbing taxa, in which the sustentacular facet is not projected laterally, and
1496 jumping taxa, in which the trochlea is compressed transversally, have low mean values of
1497 ABW. Moreover, Ginot et al. (2016) stated that fossorial, semi-fossorial and cursorial taxa
1498 show the widest astragalar head (HW), which gives flexibility to the foot independent of the

1499 ankle, while semi-aquatic taxa have the narrowest head, which greatly limits transversal
1500 movements of the foot independent of the ankle. Due to a short and more symmetrical
1501 astragalus in semi-aquatic taxa, the value of the lateral trochlear length (LTL) is lower, but is
1502 very similar in all other categories. The medial trochlear length (MTL) in climbers, fossorial
1503 and semi-fossorial taxa has lower values, and a marked asymmetry can be observed between
1504 the medial and lateral parts of the trochlea. Generalist and jumping species show a medium
1505 asymmetry. In contrast, semi-aquatic and cursorial taxa display a symmetry state in the
1506 trochlea. As the asymmetry reduces, the foot will stay more on the parasagittal plane during
1507 plantar or dorsiflexion of the foot. This will allow more efficient running and paddling (Ginot
1508 et al., 2016).

1509 The mean value of several variables measured on astragalus of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse,
1510 Persian jird, and brown rat (as terrestrial species) and was compared to those of semi-fossorial
1511 great gerbil. The values for each specimen are listed in Table 1. The mean values of ABW and
1512 HW for terrestrial group are lower than the corresponding values in the great gerbil (ABW:
1513 2.91 vs. 4.11, HW: 1.93 vs. 2.98), which is in congruence with the statements of Ginot et al.
1514 (2016). According to the study of Ginot et al. (2016), although we expect to see a higher value
1515 of ATL for the terrestrial group and a lower value of MTL for semi-fossorial species, but results
1516 are controversial: the mean value of ATL is 3.56 in the examined terrestrial group vs. 4.60 in
1517 the great gerbil, and the mean value for MTL is 1.62 for terrestrial group vs. 2.23 for the great
1518 gerbil. This can be correlated to the sample size bias. For LTL and ATW, since we have no
1519 data for any other species belonging to other locomotory categories, making a comparison is
1520 impossible. The ratio of MTL/LTL in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse was 0.77, which is higher
1521 than that of the great gerbil (0.74) (Table 1), indicating a less asymmetrical trochlea in
1522 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse. This allows the species to have more efficient running as
1523 compared to the great gerbil with semi-fossorial activity.

1524

1525 **4.5. Body mass effects on postcranium**

1526 As mentioned earlier, the extent of transmitted pressures by body weight on the postcranial
1527 skeleton can influence the morphology of bones (e.g., Christiansen, 1999; Hayssen, 2008;
1528 Scheidt et al., 2019). In spite of a lower diversity in the locomotory system of small body-sized
1529 rodents, they can share some features which are correlated to the body mass (Biewener, 1990;
1530 Christiansen, 1999).

1531 For Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, as a small rodent with the mean body weight of 19.7 g, the
1532 morphological features which are affected by body size are comparable with those of steppe
1533 field mouse (20 g) and small five-toed jerboa (39 g) (both considered as small rodents) in one
1534 hand, and Persian jird (99 g), great gerbil (170 g), and brown rat (194 g) (as three larger rodents)
1535 on the other hand as follows: Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse shows a crouched posture of the
1536 skeleton rather than an upright posture. It has a less rigid and less straight vertebral column as
1537 compared to the larger body size examined rodents. Furthermore, the overall robustness of the
1538 bones, especially limb bones and girdles, in this species is also less. Lesser robustness of
1539 femoral neck, development of the trochanteric fossa and greater trochanter of femur, with no
1540 reduction and/or caudal orientation of the lesser trochanter of femur can be also considered as
1541 postcranial features in relation to the small body size of the rodent. Furthermore, the ischium
1542 and pubic symphysis are not elongated as compared to the ilium and acetabulum.

1543 Moreover, among the studied morpho-functional indices, some showed a trend relevant to the
1544 body size; for example, SMI, GI, and TRI have lower, while CI, PES, and IM have higher
1545 values in small-sized rodents (Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, small five-toed jerboa, and
1546 steppe field mouse) as compared to the larger ones (brown rat, great gerbil, and Persian jird).
1547 For OLI and URI, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse shows the same values to the Persian jird
1548 (0.12 and 0.05, respectively) (Table 3). The same value of the first index for the two species

1549 indicates that the relative mechanical advantage of the triceps brachii and dorsoepitrochlearis
1550 muscles (used in elbow extension) is the same for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse and Persian
1551 jird, and thus, they possess a same fossorial ability. Furthermore, according to the same value
1552 of URI for the two species, the attachment site of forearm and manus flexors, pronators, and
1553 supinators, the robustness of the ulna and its ability to resist bending and shearing stresses are
1554 also identical for the both rodents. For SMI and GI, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse shows same
1555 values to the small five-toed jerboa (0.46 and 0.08, respectively) (Table 3), which means that
1556 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, as a terrestrial rodent, benefits of the same mechanical
1557 advantages of the pectoral and deltoid muscles (acting across the shoulder joint), and the gluteal
1558 muscles (used in retraction of the femur) to the saltatorial rodent, small five-toed jerboa.

1559

1560 **5. CONCLUSION**

1561 Skeletal components are useful identification tools in archeozoological and paleozoological
1562 studies, and in identifying skeletal remains in pellets of birds of prey and deposited specimens
1563 in museums as well. Integration between different parts of anatomical structures has been
1564 considered as an important determinant of phenotypic, genetic, and evolutionary variations
1565 (Jones et al., 2018). Nevertheless, the functional and evolutionary importance of morphological
1566 variations and differentiations in the postcranial skeleton is still greatly unknown.

1567 The primary objective of the present study was to describe the postcranium of a representative
1568 brush-tailed mouse species, including its functional aspects, and also to present an evolutionary
1569 insight through finding characters on which a phylogenetic classification of the family can be
1570 based or reconstructed. The information presented here would be useful for developing future
1571 comparisons between brush-tailed mice and the rest of the muroid rodents, concerning the basal
1572 location of brush-tailed mice in phylogenetic trees. Since Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse was
1573 the only species of brush-tailed mice included in our study, it is not possible to infer diagnostic
1574 morphological postcranial traits for the family Calomyscidae without the inclusion of additional
1575 representatives of the group. It is suggested to perform a detailed assessment for other species
1576 within the family. This family is highly specialized and adapted to live in generally rocky
1577 regions with a considerable range of habitat characteristics in a sole genus (Hamidi et al., 2017).
1578 Thus, it is necessary to check whether the postcranium has modified structures for that purpose.
1579 Are there any intra and interspecific morphological variations regarding the configuration of
1580 the osteological components, due to phylogenetic proximity, or related to specific variations in
1581 response to different use of habitats and/ or habits?

1582 Future investigations on other aspects of postcranial function (such as variations that occur
1583 during growth and development processes of the skeleton, muscle architecture and
1584 musculoskeletal function) are necessary for a comprehensive understanding of the postcranium.
1585 The character mapping analysis, the parsimony ancestral state reconstruction and statistical
1586 analyses are necessary for a better understanding of the function of the postcranial components
1587 in brush tailed mice, how their anatomical integration affects their function, and how the
1588 postcranial diversity is distributed throughout the family. It would be interesting to verify the
1589 influence of phylogeny on morphological variations and adaptive diversity, through the study
1590 of further quantitative and qualitative data. Hence, to evaluate whether these results represent a
1591 statistical artifice, make hypotheses about the ancestral states of these rodents, and reveal
1592 characters with a phylogenetical signal, it is necessary to include other genera of the family
1593 Calomyscidae. As indicated earlier, morphological, ecological, and behavioral features of
1594 brush-tailed mice are poorly known; with a particular evolutionary history, this group of rodents
1595 offers additional opportunities to study on the evolution of their life.

1596

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1607

1608 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT**

1609 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

1610

1611 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

1612 All the data that support the findings of this study are included in the paper. More information
1613 is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

1614

1615 **ETHICAL APPROVAL**

1616 All applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of
1617 animals were followed. All procedures performed in studies involving animals were in
1618 accordance with the ethical standards of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad.

1619

1620 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

1621 KH designed the study, collected the samples and conducted laboratory procedures, wrote the
1622 manuscript, and provided the figures and measurements. MMM conducted the methodology
1623 and had substantial contributions to the conception. MJP conducted the inferences and revising
1624 the manuscript critically for important intellectual content. CWK had scientific advices and
1625 valuable discussions about the content. JD conceived and designed the primary research line.
1626 All authors contributed in proofreading.

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2091 **Table 2** Polarity (ancestral, intermediate, and derived character states) for some of the
 2092 examined qualitative morphological characters of postcranial skeleton in the present study. For
 2093 each character, the character state which is observed in *Calomyscus elburzensis* is shown by *.
 2094 An appropriate reference(s) is also provided as the source in which a given character was
 2095 derived from, based on the illustrations or descriptions. Abbreviations are as follows: C:
 2096 Cervical vertebra, Ca: Caudal vertebra, L: Lumbar vertebra, S: Sacral vertebra, T: Thoracic
 2097 vertebra; and Ant: Anterior view, Cd: Caudal view, CM: Caudomedial view, D: Dorsal view,
 2098 Lt: Lateral view, M: Medial view, Prx: Proximal view, R: Rostral view, RL: Rostrolateral view,
 2099 RM: Rostromedial view, V: Ventral view.

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2101 **Vertebral column**

2102 *Atlas*

2103 1. Atlantal transverse process (D): low extension; short and broad* (0), high extension; long
 2104 and slender (1) (Argot, 2003; Carrizo et al., 2014).

2105 *Axis*

2106 2. Status of two axial transverse processes towards each other (V): create an arc (0), create a
 2107 hemi-arc* (1), create an angle (2) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).

2108 3. Caudal extension of axial neural process (Lt): great extension (0), little extension* (1)
 2109 (Steppan, 1995; Argot, 2003; Carrizo et al., 2014).

2110 *Seventh cervical vertebra*

2111 4. Centrum shape of C7 (R): oval* (0), semi-circular (1) (Bab et al., 2007).

2112 5. Transverse foramen of C7 (R): circular* (0), oval (1) (Bab et al., 2007).

2113 6. Form of the situation angle of carotid tubercle towards the centrum (R): vertical (0), wide*
 2114 (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).

2115 *Thoracic vertebrae*

2116 7. Total number of thoracic vertebrae: thirteen (0), twelve* (1) (Carleton, 1980; Steppan, 1995;
 2117 Pacheco, 2003).

2118 8. Shape of the neural spine tip of T2 (D): pitchfork* (0), simple (1) (Carleton, 1980; Steppan,
 2119 1995).

2120 *Second lumbar vertebra*

2121 9. Neural spine shape of L2 (D): crest-like (0), robust* (1) (Argot, 2003; Martin, 2005;
 2122 Kuncová & Frynta, 2009; Carrizo et al., 2014).

2123 *Sacral vertebrae*

2124 10. Degree of sacral curvature (Lt): little* (0), great (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).

2125 11. Shape of anterior zygapophysis (R): lunate* (0), with conic tip (1) (Bab et al., 2007).

2126 12. Status of the angle of two prezygapophyses (R): close* (0), open (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).

2127 13. Shape of intervertebral foramen: big* (0), small (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).

2128 14. The extent of the union of sacral vertebrae 1-4 (V): little; vertebral discs are visible* (0),
 2129 much; vertebral discs are going to disappear (1), so much; with disappeared vertebral discs (2)
 2130 (Bab et al., 2007).

2131 15. Connection between neural spines of S1 and S2 (Lt) is: absent* (0), present (1) (Bab et al.,
 2132 2007).

2133 16. Connection between S4 with other sacral vertebrae (Lt) is: present (0), absent* (1) (Bab et
 2134 al., 2007).

2135 *Caudal vertebrae*

2136 17. Shape of the transverse processes of first five caudal vertebrae (V): robust and short (0),
 2137 long and blade like* (1) (Argot, 2003; Carrizo et al., 2014).

2138 18. Status of transverse process of first five caudal vertebrae (V): partly divergent* (0),
 2139 completely divergent (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).

- 2140 19. Status of neural spine of Ca6 (R): completely flat (0), moderate; with partly growth (1),
 2141 completely growth* (2) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).
- 2142 20. Location of the longest caudal vertebra: in the middle of the tail length* (0), in the first 1/3
 2143 proximal of tail length (1) (Steppan, 1995).
- 2144 21. Tail length compared with the head and body length: longer* (0), equal (1), shorter (2)
 2145 (Steppan, 1995).
- 2146
- 2147 **Thoracic cage**
- 2148 ***First rib***
- 2149 22. Shape of the rib angle (R): arced* (0), nearly straight (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).
- 2150 23. An accessory uncus near the first rib tubercle (R) is: absent* (0), present (1) (Carleton,
 2151 1980).
- 2152 ***Sternum; manubrium***
- 2153 24. General shape of manubrium: short and broad (0), short and slender* (1), long and slender
 2154 (2) (Sánchez-Villagra et al., 2006).
- 2155 25. Shape of manubrium ventral crest (V): thin* (0), moderate (1), gross and robust (2) (Argot,
 2156 2003; Martin, 2005).
- 2157 26. Situation of tip of the angle of jugular notch (R): completely flat* (0), protuberant (1),
 2158 picked (2) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).
- 2159 27. Depression extent of proximal part of manubrium in apical region (R): flat* (0), with
 2160 depression (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).
- 2161
- 2162 **Pectoral girdle**
- 2163 ***Clavicle***
- 2164 28. Position of the costoclavicular ligament at the sternal end (V): not distinguishable (0),
 2165 distinguishable* (1) (Bab et al., 2007).
- 2166 ***Scapula***
- 2167 29. General shape of scapula: short and broad; with an obvious extension in the corner of the
 2168 inferior ala, and the length of the scapula is almost equal to its width (0), short and slender;
 2169 doesn't have an obvious extension in the corner of inferior ala, and the length of the scapula is
 2170 almost 1.5 times longer than its width* (1), long and slender; the length of the scapula is almost
 2171 two times bigger than its width (2) (Argot, 2003; Martin, 2005; Seckel & Janis, 2008; Kuncová
 2172 & Frynta, 2009).
- 2173 30. Posterior extension of the caudal angle (D) is: absent (0), present* (1) (Coutinho & de
 2174 Oliveira, 2017).
- 2175 31. Angle between the cranial and vertebral borders (D) is: absent* (0), present (1) (Coutinho
 2176 & de Oliveira, 2017).
- 2177 32. Relative length of supraspinous and infraspinous fossas (D): supraspinous > infraspinous
 2178 (0), supraspinous < infraspinous* (1), supraspinous = infraspinous (2) (Coutinho & de Oliveira,
 2179 2017).
- 2180 33. Status of superior process of scapula spine (D): little significant* (0), significant (1),
 2181 completely significant and prominent (2) (Martin, 2005; Seckel & Janis, 2008; Morgan, 2009).
- 2182 34. Curvature point of acromion process (D): to the rostral region* (0), straight (1) (Bab et al.,
 2183 2007).
- 2184 35. Extension of the acromion process (D): beyond the coracoid (surpassing the coracoid) (0),
 2185 same extension as the coracoid (1), anterior to the coracoid* (2) (Coutinho & de Oliveira,
 2186 2017).
- 2187 36. Coracoid process shape (Lt): hook-like* (0), small (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

2188 37. Curvature extent of coracoid process of scapula (Lt): straight* (0), up to the superior ridge
2189 of glenoid fossa (1), up to the middle of glenoid fossa (2) (Carleton, 1980; Sánchez-Villagra et
2190 al., 2006).

2191

2192 **Forelimb**

2193 ***Humerus***

2194 38. Shape of humeral head (Cd): elongated (0), rounded* (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

2195 39. Posterior projection of the head (Lt) is: absent (0), present* (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira,
2196 2017).

2197 40. The relative height of the greater tuberosity (in relation to the humeral head) (Cd): lower*
2198 (0), same height (1), higher (2) (Szalay & Sargis, 2001; Candela & Picasso, 2008; Coutinho &
2199 de Oliveira, 2017).

2200 41. Status of the tip of the deltoid tuberosity (RM): slender and forming a thin blade* (0), thick,
2201 assuming a globular shape (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

2202 42. Status of deltoid tuberosity towards the shaft (body) of humerus (RM): form a lunate* (0),
2203 form a hook (1) (Steppan, 1995; Sánchez-Villagra et al., 2006).

2204 43. Depth of the groove associated with ulnar nerve (Cd): little* (0), great (1) (Argot, 2003;
2205 Sánchez-Villagra et al., 2006).

2206 44. The shape of coronoid fossa (Cd): open* (0), closed (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

2207 45. The medial epicondyle tip (Cd) is: absent* (0), present (0) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

2208 46. Entepicondylar foramen in epiphysis zone of humerus (Cd) is: present (0), absent* (1)
2209 (Carleton, 1980; Steppan, 1995; Pacheco, 2003).

2210 47. Distal extension of the capitulum and trochlea (Cd): capitulum > trochlea (0), same
2211 extension (1), trochlea > capitulum* (2) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

2212 ***Ulna***

2213 48. Depression extent of olecranon (CM): significant (great)* (0), moderate (1), little (2) (Bab
2214 et al., 2007).

2215 49. Shape of olecranon superior ridge of ulna (RL): curved* (0), flat (1) (Rose & Chinnery,
2216 2004).

2217 50. The medial curvature of olecranon process (R) is: absent (0), slightly curved* (1), greatly
2218 curved (2) (Vassallo, 1998; Lessa et al., 2008; Carrizo et al., 2014).

2219 51. The medial extension of the medial coronoid crest (R) is: absent* (0), present (1) (The
2220 medial olecranon crest used as the frame of reference: if the ulnar medial coronoid crest
2221 surpasses the medial olecranon crest, it is present, and if it does not surpass, it means absent)
2222 (Flores, 2009; Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

2223 52. Shape of ulnar tuberosity (CM): linear and crest-like* (0), gross and robust (1) (Samuels &
2224 Van Valkenburgh, 2008; Seckel & Janis, 2008).

2225 53. A small tubercle on the medial edge of the ulnar shaft (R) is: present* (0), absent (1) (Bab
2226 et al., 2007).

2227 54. Shape of semi-lunar notch (RL): semi-circular* (0), triangular (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).

2228 55. The longitudinal groove (RL) is: absent (0), shallow (1), deep* (2) (Coutinho & de Oliveira,
2229 2017).

2230 ***Radius***

2231 56. Radial head shape (Prx): elliptical* (0), circular (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

2232 57. Convex degree of the radius shaft (M): little (0), great* (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).

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2234 **Pelvic girdle**

2235 ***Innominate bone***

2236 58. Acetabulum outline (Lt): complete (0), incomplete* (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).

- 2237 59. Depth of the acetabulum (Lt): shallow, absence of the large acetabulum outline* (0), deep,
 2238 presence of the large acetabulum outline (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).
- 2239 60. Ilium shape (Lt): curved* (0), straight (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).
- 2240 61. Iliac wing forming a large blade (Lt) is: absent* (0), present (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira,
 2241 2017).
- 2242 62. Shape of the contour of iliopectinal eminence (Lt): curved* (0), picked (1), indeterminate
 2243 (2) (Argot, 2003; Martin, 2005; Kuncová & Frynta, 2009).
- 2244 63. Shape of pubis tubercle (Lt): picked* (0), not picked, arced (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).
- 2245 64. Situation of tip of pubis angle in relation to the anterior arc of obturator foramen (Lt): in
 2246 front of the middle superior of anterior arc (0), lower than 1/2 inferior of anterior arc (1), in
 2247 front of 1/3 inferior of anterior arc* (2) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).
- 2248 65. Length of pubic symphysis as compared with the distance between the tip of pubis angle
 2249 and iliopectinal eminence (Lt): longer (0), shorter* (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).
- 2250 66. Size of pubic symphysis in relation to the craniocaudal size of the obturator foramen (Lt):
 2251 smaller* (0), equal (1), larger (2) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).
- 2252 67. Amount of protuberance of the tuberosity of ischium (Lt): great (0), little* (1) (Argot,
 2253 2003).
- 2254 68. Caudal portion of ischium body curved laterally (Lt) is: absent (0), present* (1) (Coutinho
 2255 & de Oliveira, 2017).
- 2256 69. Shape of the ridge of body of ischium around the tuberosity of ischium (Lt): triangular (0),
 2257 arced* (1) (Bab et al., 2007).
- 2258 70. Curvature shape of posterior arc of obturator foramen (Lt): with a triangular-like posterior
 2259 curvature* (0), with a semi-circular-like posterior curvature (1), parallel with anterior arc (2)
 2260 (Bab et al., 2007).
- 2261
- 2262 **Hindlimb**
- 2263 **Femur**
- 2264 71. Femoral head shape (R): more hemi-spheric (0), more spherical* (1) (Coutinho & de
 2265 Oliveira, 2017).
- 2266 72. Status of femoral trochanteric fossa (Cd): narrow* (0), deep and wide (1) (Rose &
 2267 Chinnery, 2004).
- 2268 73. Anterior intertrochanteric crest (Cd) is: absent (0), little developed (1), well developed* (2)
 2269 (Bab et al., 2007).
- 2270 74. Small uncus near the femoral greater trochanter (R) is: present (0), absent* (1) (Hamidi et
 2271 al., 2020a).
- 2272 75. The projection of the lesser trochanter from the margin of femur (Cd) is: posteromedially*
 2273 (0), medially (1) (Argot, 2002; Candela & Picasso, 2008; Carrizo et al., 2014; Coutinho & de
 2274 Oliveira, 2017).
- 2275 76. Position of lesser trochanter toward femur shaft (Cd): create a lunate* (0), create an angle
 2276 (1) (Hamidi et al., 2020a).
- 2277 77. Lesser trochanter (Cd) is: underdeveloped* (0), developed (1) (Coutinho & de Oliveira,
 2278 2017).
- 2279 78. Degree of thickening of the third trochanter (R): slender* (0), thick (1) (Coutinho & de
 2280 Oliveira, 2017).
- 2281 79. Distal extension of medial and lateral condyles (R): medial condyle is more extended (0),
 2282 show same extension (1), lateral condyle is more extended* (2) (Coutinho & de Oliveira, 2017).
- 2283 780. Shape of distal metaphysis ridge (Cd): without ridge (0), with a short ridge* (1), with an
 2284 eminent ridge (2) (Bab et al., 2007).
- 2285 **Tibia**

2286 81. A crest in the soleal line (RL) is: absent (0), underdeveloped (1), developed* (2) (Coutinho
2287 & de Oliveira, 2017).

2288 ***Calcaneus***

2289 82. Status of calcaneus posterior tuberosity (V): explicit* (0), developed (1) (Carleton, 1980;
2290 Sánchez-Villagra et al., 2006).

2291 83. Status of the groove for the tendon of flexor hallucis longus muscle (M): deep* (0), shallow
2292 (1) (Bab et al., 2007).

2293 84. Shape of cuboid articular surface of calcaneus (Ant): rounded to oval* (0), triangular (1),
2294 quadrangular (2) (Sánchez-Villagra et al., 2006; Weisbecker & Schmid, 2007; Carrizo et al.,
2295 2014).

2296 ***Astragalus***

2297 85. Status of astragalus groove (V): deep* (0), shallow (1) (Weisbecker & Schmid, 2007).

2298 ***Third metatarsal bone***

2299 86. Shape of third metatarsal bone: normal* (0), short and robust (1) (Pacheco, 2003; Sánchez-
2300 Villagra et al., 2006).

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FIGURE 1 Cervical vertebrae of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a-d) Atlas in rostral, dorsal, ventral, and lateral views, respectively. (e-h) Axis in rostral, dorsal, ventral, and lateral views, respectively. (i-l) Third cervical vertebra in rostral, dorsal, ventral, and lateral views, respectively. (m-o) Fourth, fifth and sixth cervical vertebrae in rostral view, respectively. Fifth cervical vertebra is partly broken. (p-s) Seventh cervical vertebra in rostral, dorsal, ventral, and lateral views, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows: atlantal transverse process (ATTP), axial neural process (AXNP), axial transverse process (AXTP), centrum of seventh cervical vertebra (CC), carotid tubercle of seventh cervical vertebra (CCT), and transverse foramen of seventh cervical vertebra (CTF).

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FIGURE 2 Thoracic vertebrae of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a,b) First thoracic vertebra in rostral and lateral views, respectively. (c,d) Second thoracic vertebra in rostral and dorsal views, respectively. (e-j) Third to eighth thoracic vertebrae in rostral view, respectively. (k-m) Tenth to twelfth thoracic vertebrae in rostral view, respectively. Thoracic vertebra 9 is not shown. Abbreviations are as follows: neural spine of first thoracic vertebra (TNS), prezygapophysis of first thoracic vertebra (TPRZP), and transverse process of first thoracic vertebra (TPZ).

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FIGURE 3 Lumbar vertebrae of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a-d) Second lumbar vertebra in rostral, dorsal, ventral, and lateral views, respectively. (e,f) Third lumbar vertebra in rostral and dorsal views, respectively. (g,h) Fifth lumbar vertebra in rostral and dorsal views, respectively. Lumbar vertebrae 1 and 4 are not shown. (i-l) Sacral vertebrae 1-4 (sacrum) in rostral, dorsal, ventral, and lateral views, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows: neural spine of second lumbar vertebra (LNS), prezygapophysis of second lumbar vertebra (LPZ), transverse process of second lumbar vertebra (LTP), sacral intervertebral foramen (SIF), sacral median crest (SMC), prezygapophysis of first sacral vertebra (SPZP), transverse process of first sacral vertebra (STP).

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FIGURE 4 Caudal vertebrae of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a,b) First caudal vertebra in rostral and dorsal views, respectively. (c) First to fifth caudal vertebrae in ventral view. (d-f) Sixth caudal vertebra in rostral, dorsal, and ventral views, respectively. (g-z'') Caudal vertebrae 7-28 in dorsal view, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows: neural spine of first caudal vertebra (CANS), prezygapophysis of first caudal vertebra (CAPZP), transverse process of first caudal vertebra (CATP).

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FIGURE 5 Bones of the thoracic cage of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a) First rib in rostral view. (b,c) Manubrium in dorsal and ventral views, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows: tubercle of first rib (FRT) and jugular notch of manubrium (JN).

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FIGURE 6 Pectoral girdle of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a) Clavicle in ventral view. (b-d) Scapula in dorsal, dorsoposterior, and lateral views, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows: acromial end of clavicle (AE), glenoid fossa of scapula (GF), infraspinous fossa (ISF), acromion process of scapula (SAP), acromion ramus of scapula (SAR), caudal angle of scapula (SCA), coracoid process of scapula (SCP), sternal end of clavicle (SE), scapular neck (SNK), superior process of scapula spine (SPSS), scapular spine (SS), supraspinous fossa (SSF).

2387 **FIGURE 7** Forelimb of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a-c)
 2388 Humerus in caudal, rostromedial, and lateral views, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows:
 2389 capitulum (CA), coronoid fossa (CF), coronoid-olecranon notch (CON), deltoid tuberosity
 2390 (DT), capitulum-trochlea groove (G), greater tubercle (GT), head of humerus (or humeral head)
 2391 (HH), posterior projection of humeral head (HPP), lateral epicondyle (LE), lesser tubercle
 2392 (LT), medial epicondyle (ME), olecranon notch (ON), radial fossa (RF), supinator crest (SC),
 2393 supratrochlear foramen (STF), trochlea (TR).
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FIGURE 8 Forelimb of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a-c) Ulna in rostralateral, rostral, and caudomedial views, respectively. (d,e) Radius in medial and caudal views, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows: articular surface for the humeral capitulum (ASHC), articular surface for ulna (ASU), head of radius (HR), lateral coronoid crest (LCC), longitudinal groove (LG), lateral olecranon crest (LOC), medial coronoid crest (MCC), medial olecranon crest (MOC), olecranon (O), olecranon superior ridge (OSR), radial notch (RN), radial ridge (RR), radial tuberosity (RT), semi-lunar notch (SN), styloid process of radius (SPR), styloid process of ulna (SPU), tubercle of ulnar shaft (T), ulnar coronoid process (UCP), ulnar olecranon process (UOP), ulnar tuberosity (UT).

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FIGURE 9 (a) Anterior autopodium of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (b-e) Metacarpal bones 5-2, respectively. (f-i) Proximal phalange of digits 5-2, respectively. (j-m) Intermediate phalange of digits 5-2, respectively. First digit and terminal phalanges of all digits are missed. Abbreviations are as follows: intermediate phalange of digit (IPH), metacarpal bone (MC), proximal phalange of digit (PPH).

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 2413 **FIGURE 10** Pelvic girdle of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a,b)
 2414 Innominate bone in lateral and medial views, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows:
 2415 anterior inferior iliac spine (AIIS), acetabular notch (AN), iliac crest (IC), iliopectinal eminence
 2416 (IE), ischial spine (IS), ischial tuberosity (IT), iliac wing (IW), obturator foramen (OF), pubis
 2417 angle (PA), pubic symphysis (PS), pubis tuber (PT).

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FIGURE 11 Hindlimb of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a-c) Femur in rostral, caudal, and proximal views, respectively. (d,e) Tibia and fibula in rostralateral and proximal views, respectively. Abbreviations are as follows: fovea capitis (FC), femoral lateral condyle (FLC), femoral medial condyle (FMC), femoral neck (FN), femoral trochanteric fossa (FTF), greater trochanter (GTR), head of the femur (HFE), head of fibula (HFI), head of tibia (HT), intercondylar fossa (ICF), intercondylar groove of tibia (IG), intertrochanteric crest (ITC), lateral malleolus (LM), lesser trochanter (LTR), medial malleolus (MM), ridge of distal metaphysis of femur (R), crest in the soleal line (SLC), tibial crest (TC), tibial lateral condyle (TLC), tibial medial condyle (TMC), tibial ridge (TRD), trochlear groove for patella (TRGP), tibial tuberosity (TT), third trochanter (TTR).

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FIGURE 12 (a) Posterior mesopodium of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (a-d) Calcaneus in dorsal, ventral, medial, and anterior views, respectively. (e) Astragalus in ventral view. Abbreviations are as follows: anterior facet for astragalus (AFA), astragalus head (AH), cuboid articular surface (CAS), calcaneal tuberosity (CT), groove for the tendon of flexor hallucis longus muscle (GT), lateral articular surface (LAS), lateral malleolar surface (LMS), medial articular surface (MAS), medial malleolar surface (MMS), astragalus neck (N), sulcus of astragalus (ST), trochlea arc (TA).

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FIGURE 13 (a) Posterior autopodium of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (b-f) Metatarsal bones 5-1, respectively. (g-k) Proximal phalange of digits 5-1, respectively. (l-o) Intermediate phalange of digits 5-2, respectively. (p) Terminal phalange of digit 4. Terminal phalange of other digits are missed. Abbreviations are as follows: intermediate phalange of digit (IPH), metatarsal bone (MT), proximal phalange of digit (PPH), terminal phalange of digit (TPH).

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 2453 **FIGURE 15** Bivariate diagrams of length and width of postcranium for examined species: (a)
 2454 SL and WS of sacrum, (b) LLV and WLW of last lumbar vertebra, (c) LS and WS1 of scapula,
 2455 (d) LH and HMLD of humerus, (e) LU and UMLD of ulna, (f) (LI+LIP) and WIP of innominate
 2456 bone, (g) LF and FAPD of femur, and (h) LT and TMLD of tibia. Measurements for
 2457 *Calomyscus elburzensis*, *Meriones persicus*, *Rattus norvegicus*, *Rhombomys opimus*, and
 2458 *Scarturus elater* were done during this study, while those of *Apodemus witherbyi* were
 2459 extracted from Kuncová & Frynta (2009). See Table 1 for abbreviated variables names, and
 2460 Figure 14 for more details.

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FIGURE 16 Scaling plot of morpho-functional indices of forelimb for examined species: (a) Shoulder moment index (SMI), (b) Brachial index (BI), (c) Humeral robustness index (HRI), (d) Humeral epicondylar index (HEB), (e) Olecranon length index (OLI), (f) Ulnar robustness index (URI), and (g) Manus proportions index (MANUS). Detailed descriptions of indices and measurements are included in Table 1 and 3. Species ID no. are associated with Table 3. Species number 10 is indicating *Calomyscus elburzensis* which is shown with red circle. Abbreviations for locomotion type are as follows: AE: Aerial, AR: Arboreal, FO: Fossorial, SA: Semi-aquatic, SF: Semi-fossorial, ST: Saltatorial, TE: Terrestrial.

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FIGURE 17 Scaling plot of morpho-functional indices of hindlimb (part A) for examined species: (a) Crural index (CI), (b) Gluteal index (GI), (c) Femoral robustness index (FRI), (d) Femoral epicondylar index (FEI). Detailed descriptions of indices and measurements are included in Table 1 and 3. Species ID no. are associated with Table 3. Species number 10 is indicating *Calomyscus elburzensis* which is shown with red circle. Abbreviations for locomotion type are as follows: AE: Aerial, AR: Arboreal, FO: Fossorial, SA: Semi-aquatic, SF: Semi-fossorial, ST: Saltatorial, TE: Terrestrial.

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FIGURE 18 Scaling plot of morpho-functional indices of hindlimb (part B) for examined species: (a) Tibial robustness index (TRI), (b) Tibial spine index (TSI), (c) Pes length index (PES), (d) Intermembral index (IM). Detailed descriptions of indices and measurements are included in Table 1 and 3. Species ID no. are associated with Table 3. Species number 10 is indicating *Calomyscus elburzensis* which is shown with red circle. Abbreviations for locomotion type are as follows: AE: Aerial, AR: Arboreal, FO: Fossorial, SA: Semi-aquatic, SF: Semi-fossorial, ST: Saltatorial, TE: Terrestrial.

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FIGURE 19 Burrow entrances of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). Burrows are simple and made of superficial excavation or a slight alteration of pre-existing hollows (a), crevices (b), or natural refuges provided by big stones (c).